

Deliverable D1.1

Initial report on policy obstacles and opportunities for the integration and uptake of citizen generated data and citizen & community-led actions in environmental compliance assurance

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Executive summary

The current document, titled ‘Initial report on policy obstacles and opportunities for the integration and uptake of citizen generated data and citizen & community-led actions in environmental compliance assurance’, has been developed within the framework of the more4nature project which is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement 101133983.

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This report, as a contribution to the overall aim of the more4nature project, provides a sound understanding – based on a representative sample of international and regional policies – of the status quo regarding the role of citizen & community-led actions (CCLA) and citizen generated data (CGD) in environmental policies with regards to environmental compliance assurance (ECA). The concept of ‘citizen & community-led actions’ is being developed as part of the more4nature project and refers to actions that citizens and communities can take to improve environmental protection. CGD is often the product of actions by citizens and can notably be used to complement institutional data.

The policy analysis in this report takes place within the context of the three thematic policy areas of the more4nature project, namely zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention (Z/B/D).

This report analyses the three types of intervention of ECA in light of possible use of citizen science, and more specifically:

- Whether CCLA can be used in compliance *promotion*, i.e. to contribute to preventing and limiting non-compliance with a policy;
- Whether CGD can be used in compliance *monitoring*, i.e. to track and identify potential problems with compliance; and
- Whether CCLA and/or CGD can be used in compliance *enforcement*, i.e. to address, via legal or official channels, a situation of non-compliance.

Twenty policies were selected for analysis in this report. Each of them was reviewed using selected keywords and a template resulting from a multidisciplinary collaboration with project partners. Every step and stages of the iterative methodological approach developed, implemented and refined to conduct the policy analysis is presented in detail:

- Step 1: Preparations, including the selection of policies, the selection of criteria and keywords, and the development of the template;
- Step 2: the policy analysis, i.e. the initial data collection, the review process and the collection of completed data;
- Step 3: the data analysis, including results extraction, identification of trends and preliminary findings, and drafting of the report.

The preliminary findings show that ECA is largely a matter of national competence, whether a policy is adopted at EU or international level. Therefore, most policies analysed did not include

many provisions or other specifications about how to conduct ECA. Generally, compliance enforcement was the type of intervention that was least present from policy texts.

We found that in the policies we analysed, the terms used to refer to some forms of citizen involvement were mostly not those that define citizens science in the literature. Instead, the most relevant terms that we came across included ‘public’, ‘civil society’, ‘third parties’, ‘stakeholders’, ‘consultation’ and ‘participation’. With regards to the use of CCLA in compliance promotion, the most common occurrences referred to the provision of information to citizens, although some also included requirement of consultation or active public participation. The use of CGD in compliance monitoring was rarely directly specified in the policies, but some provisions contained elements that indicated either that such use could be possible or, on the contrary, that it could be restricted. In the latter case, the existence or extent of such restriction would most often depend on the interpretation of the international or EU provisions at the national level. The use of CCLA and CGD in compliance enforcement ranged among the policies, with some having minimal enforcement provisions and others allowing access to the public in judicial procedures (as applicants or as witnesses).

Most opportunities for the use of CCLA and CGD in ECA were found in one horizontal policy - the Aarhus Convention on access to information, public participation in decision-making and access to justice in environmental matters, as well as in the most recently adopted Z/B/D policies that we assessed, namely Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 on Deforestation-free Products and the 2022 Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, the Environmental Crime Directive and the Nature Restoration Regulation (also known as ‘Nature Restoration Law’). These policies may show the way in terms of how future policies or revisions of existing ones may better promote the use of citizen science in ECA. However, it should be noted that our findings are based on an analysis of the text of selected policies and may not necessarily translate in practice.

This report demonstrates that, on the one hand, there are opportunities for the use of CCLA and CGD in ECA within the EU and international context. Those are quite varied and stem both from horizontal and vertical policies. On the other hand, the report also exposes the difficulty of identifying such opportunities in environmental policies because of the vagueness of the language or the referral to the national (or local) level to decide whether to allow or restrict the use of CCLA and CGD. This may give room for agency through interpretation, but effectively leaves citizen science groups in the dark about how policies enable or even promote their participation in the ECA process.

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
B	Biodiversity protection
CCLA	Citizen & Community-led Actions
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CGD	Citizen Generated Data
D	Deforestation prevention
DoA	Description of the Action
EC	European Commission
ECA	Environmental Compliance Assurance
EU	European Union
F2F	Face-to-Face
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GBF	Kunming-Montreal global biodiversity framework
H	Horizontal (cross-cutting)
M	Month of the project
MEA	Multilateral Environmental Agreement
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SSH	Social Science and Humanities
TEU	Treaty on European Union
TFEU	Treaty for the Functioning of the European Union
UN	United Nations

UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
UNEP	United Nations Environmental Programme
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
WP	Work Package
Z	Zero pollution

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1. Introduction

This report is the first output of Task 1.1 of the more4nature project. The purpose of the report is to present an initial policy mapping focusing on obstacles and opportunities for the integration and uptake of citizen & community-led actions (CCLA) and citizen generated data (CGD) in environmental compliance assurance (ECA) in selected EU and international policies related to zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention (Z/B/D).

1.1. The more4nature project

The more4nature aims to trigger transformative change in efforts regarding zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention by including citizens and communities as key actors in collaborative **environmental compliance assurance (ECA)**. A key element in reversing the trend in environmental degradation is a change in environmental compliance assurance interventions. **Citizen science initiatives** present innovative ways of joint data and knowledge production and of empowering citizens in sustainable natural resource management. However, barriers to the uptake of **citizen generated data (CGD)** and **citizen & community-led actions (CCLA)** in ECA have not been effectively tackled.

The more4nature project uses a socio-technical approach to address these challenges and deepen the role of citizens and communities in ECA by:

- i) strengthening the capacity of existing citizen science initiatives to provide relevant and valid data and understanding the importance of ECA,
- ii) fostering and supporting collaboration and partnerships among citizen science initiatives and authorities to cover data gaps and shape policy monitoring frameworks,
- iii) developing and testing tools to validate data obtained from citizen science Initiatives, thus contributing to the integration of such data sources in environmental governance and in European Open Science Cloud,
- iv) making CGD available as a node in the Green Deal Data Space,
- v) creating synergies between Citizen science initiatives and Living Labs and other initiatives such as Fab Labs, which can help co-design actions as part of green and digital transformations.

The aim of more4nature is to strengthen the role of citizen science in ECA. Thus, the project takes as a starting point that CCLA and CGD can contribute to better compliance with Z/B/D policies as well as serving as drivers for policy change.

In the writing of the project proposal, the project partners identified two ways in which CCLA and CGD respectively could serve more specifically to promote ECA. On the one hand, CGD appears particularly suited to contribute to compliance monitoring and enforcement, because both processes require data that public authorities often struggle to gather sufficiently due to lack of time and resources, or lack of proximity to the area in question. On the other hand, CCLAs are expected to best support compliance promotion and enforcement. These are assumptions under which this initial report was developed in accordance with the project's methodology (see Deliverable 3.1) and visualized in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. The more4nature conceptual framework. Source: More4nature.

The more4nature project consists of six interrelated work packages (WPs): This report (Deliverable 1.1) is part of **WP1** on social dimensions of empowering citizens and citizen science initiatives in collaborative ECA. **WP2** (Technical Dimension: Geospatial modelling with FAIR CGD. From validated CGD to spatialized policy indicators) aims to provide the necessary technical developments for the project to operate successfully. **WP3** is dedicated to the Case studies related to zero pollution, biodiversity protection or deforestation prevention, starting with 20 Pioneer cases described in the Description of the Action (DoA) of the more4nature project (1st cycle), and followed by 20 Followers cases (2nd cycle). Using a tailored co-design methodology, the project aims to trigger changes in real-life setting of these cases by supporting them in their respective journey towards collaborative ECA. **WP4** relates to Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation, and includes notably a task on the strategic engagement of policy makers and national agencies (T4.5). **WP5** focuses on Project Management and **WP6** on Ethics requirements.

More details about the project can be found on the project website: <https://more4nature.eu/>

1.2. Relation of Task 1.1 to the rest of the project

This deliverable is the outcome of the first phase (Phase 1 corresponding to months 1 to 6 of the project) of Task 1.1 ‘Policy context: obstacles & opportunities in international and EU policies for integration of citizen actions and CGD in compliance promotion, monitoring and enforcement’.

The aim of Task 1.1 is to analyse obstacles and opportunities in relevant international and EU Z/D/B related policies that can affect the uptake of CCLA and CGD in compliance promotion, monitoring and enforcement. The EU and international policy landscapes are mapped and analysed in terms of their fitness to facilitate the integration of CCLA and CGD in ECA. Within Task 1.1, a cross-cutting coherence assessment aims to look at synergies and/or inconsistencies between the Z/B/D policy areas to foster harmonisation and learning opportunities. Insights from

Task 1.1 will notably feed into the project policy briefs for the strategic engagement of policy makers and national agencies regarding effective integration of citizen science initiatives in policy development and implementation to be prepared by T4.5. Identified policy challenges will be further explored in the case studies in WP3 to find out how certain policy challenges affect compliance assurance practices at the national and/or subnational governance level.

In Phase 2 of Task 1.1 (i.e. from months 7 to 24 of the project), we will also provide the methodological approach for the collection and assessment of (sub)national policies within each case study as well as the analytical framework for case study leaders to explore compliance frameworks within their cases and compare the organisation of ECA across other cases and policy areas.

A final report on policy obstacles and opportunities for the integration and uptake of CCLA and CGD in ECA (Deliverable 1.9) is due in month 24 of the project building further on this report (Deliverable 1.1, due month 6) and the additional work described above.

1.3. Structure of the report

The results presented in this initial report are based on the analysis of selected policies and a list of policy criteria developed by the task lead (NIVA) together with the more4nature partners. The report is structured within four chapters, in addition to having an executive summary and annexes.

Chapter 2 provides a short background in the evolution of environmental policymaking at international and EU level and introduces the type of policy instruments used in the field, and which form the basis for the analysis in this report. This chapter also provides definitions of the key terms and concepts used in this report, including ECA and the three types of interventions – namely compliance promotion, compliance monitoring and compliance enforcement – as well as horizontal policies, and the thematic policy areas, namely zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention. It also includes a discussion on the terms ‘citizen science’, CCLA and CGD and how they are used in this project.

Chapter 3 sets out the methodological framework of the policy analysis focusing on the iterative methodological approach developed, implemented, and refined to conduct the policy analysis, as well as a discussion on the limitations of the approach.

Chapter 4 outlines preliminary results, describing how the regulatory framework is guiding ECA and assessing the extent to which a selection of related EU or international policies encourage or restrict CCLA and CGD within compliance promotion, monitoring, or enforcement. This chapter finishes with overarching takeaways from the analysis.

Finally, Chapter 5 consists of a concluding summary of the analytical approach, important results, and potential next steps. The annexes include the template developed and used to characterize policy inclusion of CCLA and CGD in ECA.

2. Background and definitions

This chapter aims to provide some background information to make this report more accessible and useful to those who are less familiar with international and EU environmental policies and policy analysis. It also establishes some key definitions that form the basis for the analysis.

2.1. Short introduction to international and EU environmental policymaking and policy instruments

In Task 1.1, the focus of the policy analysis is on international and EU environmental policies. Environmental policymaking has accelerated a lot since the 1950s, and even more in the last decades with a multiplication of policies and laws addressing most environmental media and sources of pollution. This section provides a short introduction to the evolution of environmental policymaking and ECA at international and EU level and presents the different types of policy instruments discussed in this report. The aim is to introduce the readers to the different policymaking approaches and the impact of the type of instruments on the content and compliance mechanisms.

2.1.1. The international level

At the international level, the UN has been the main forum for the adoption of Multilateral Environmental Agreements (MEAs), but there are also regional fora. MEAs are the result of intergovernmental negotiations; the first among them was the Ramsar Convention, signed in 1971 to protect wetlands of significance to migratory waterbirds. They can be legally binding, non-legally binding or partially legally binding, as in the case of the Paris Agreement. Legally binding instruments may take the form of treaties, (framework) conventions, agreements or protocols. Non-legally binding instruments would typically be declarations, environmental action plans, principles, guidelines, codes of conduct, and recommendations. Legally binding acts are often referred to as ‘hard law’. They are authoritative and prescriptive, and result in legally enforceable obligations for the state and other international subjects (where relevant). The Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer, considered to be among the most successful MEAs, set legally binding targets for phasing out ozone depleting substances (Mader et al., 2010).

‘Soft laws’ are, by contrast, a residue category that comprises legal rules for which one or more of three dimensions – obligation, precision and delegation – has been weakened (Schaffer and Pollack, 2010; Abbott and Snidal, 2000). These laws usually seek to change or guide behaviours and set norms with a high degree of structure and formalization yet without creating rights or obligations by themselves (Daly, 2021). The value of soft laws lies notably in “flexibility when dealing with uncertainty, enabling learning processes, accommodating power differentials and retaining decision-making power, lower probability of violation and thus audience cost, as well as higher attainability and compliance” (Wanner, 2021). For example, the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) can be considered as soft law instruments. The SDGs have stronger and more universal support notably because they are non-binding and allow for more flexibility in their implementation (Harrington, 2021).

Signatories to binding or partially binding MEAs are countries that have expressed an intention to comply with the MEA. It is only upon ratification, however, that the state legally agrees to comply with an MEA and to adopt legislative or executive law to implement it. In this sense, compliance with international environmental law remains largely a matter of national competence.

Compliance promotion in international environmental policy is most often conducted through incentives or disincentives, or forms of assistance including education, financial, technical assistance, and knowledge transfer (Brunnée, 2011). Compliance promotion is often directed to regulated entities such that they better understand or are prepared to meet compliance requirements (OECD, 2009).

Most MEAs include some form of compliance mechanisms that may include the following elements (UNEP, 2006b):

1. A requirement for information reviewing national performance of MEA obligations ('performance review information');
2. Institutionalized multilateral procedures to consider apparent instances of non-compliance ('multilateral non-compliance procedures');
3. Multilateral measures adopted to respond to non-compliance ('non-compliance response measures'); and
4. Dispute settlement procedures.

The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) is the only example of an MEA for which an independent judicial body – the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea – was established. The tribunal has jurisdiction over disputes related to the interpretation or implementation of the convention.

Some Conventions, such as the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) or the Basel Convention on the Control of Transboundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and Their Disposal (Basel Convention), have a Conference of the Parties (COP), which is the supreme decision-making body of the Convention. The role of the COP is to review the implementation of the Convention and any other legal instruments that the COP adopts. It also takes decisions necessary to promote the effective implementation of the Convention, including institutional and administrative arrangements. All States that are Parties to the Convention are represented at the COP (see Rules of Procedure¹). Enforcement mechanisms through civil or criminal arbitration are rare, and in many MEAs there are no such mechanisms in place, or often left to states to decide (Brunnée, 2011; UNEP, 2006a; Interpol 2018).

2.1.2. The EU level

The Treaty on the European Union (TEU) and the Treaty for the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) lay down the objectives of the EU, the rules governing its institutions, the decision-making processes and the division of competences between the EU and its Member States. Thus, Article 4 of the TFEU establishes that the area of environmental protection is a shared competence between the Union and the Member States. The specific EU competence to adopt environmental policies and law derives from Article 11 (principle of integration) and 191-3 TFEU. The European Commission is a key player in the policymaking process. It can issue Communications that may notably contain explanations of action-programmes, brief outlines on future policies or arrangements concerning details of current policy. The role of the European Commission is also to propose legislation, which – in the field of environmental law – are then to be adopted by the two EU legislators, namely the European Parliament and the Council, in accordance with the ordinary legislative procedure set out in Article 294 TFEU. Furthermore, the European Commission is responsible for ensuring that EU policies and laws are correctly applied across EU countries (see more below at 2.2.1)

EU policies may be implemented through different types of legislative instruments, the most important of which are directives and regulations. *Directives* are legislative acts that define common goals, but leave individual Member States to adopt or adapt national legislation in order to achieve these goals. On the other hand, *Regulations* apply directly and equally across the Member States. The transposition of Regulations into national legislation does not in principle require national rules to enter into effect. There are also a number of other instruments including

¹ cbd.int

decisions (legally binding), recommendations and opinions (non-legally binding) that the various EU institutions can have recourse to, the nature (i.e. legislative or non-legislative) of which depends notably on which authority adopts them. The European Commission can also adopt communications (sometimes also referred to as strategies or action plans) and working papers that are non-legislative – the European Commission is not a legislative authority – and non-binding legal acts. In addition, the European Commission can adopt delegated acts or implementing acts that are non-legislative, but legally binding acts aimed at specifying EU law and thus ensuring it is implemented properly. The overview of the main EU legal instruments of relevance for this report is provided in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Main types of EU legal instruments and definitions

Legal act	Nature	Authority	Definition
Directive	Legislative and legally binding	European Parliament and Council of the EU	A directive shall be binding, as to the result to be achieved, upon each Member State to which it is addressed, but shall leave to the national authorities the choice of form and methods (Article 288 TFEU)
Regulation	Legislative and legally binding	European Parliament and Council of the EU	A regulation shall have general application. It shall be binding in its entirety and directly applicable in all Member States (Article 288 TFEU)
Decision	Legislative or non-legislative and legally binding	European Parliament and Council of the EU, Council of the EU or European Commission	A decision shall be binding in its entirety. A decision which specifies those to whom it is addressed shall be binding only on them (Article 288 TFEU)
Recommendation and opinion	Non-legislative and non-legally binding	European Parliament, Council of the EU, European Commission, Committee of the Regions or European Economic and Social Committee	A recommendation and an opinion shall have no binding force (Article 288 TFEU)
Communication	Non-legislative and non-legally binding	European Commission	Not mentioned in the Treaties
Working paper/staff working paper	Non-legislative and non-legally binding	European Commission	Not mentioned in the Treaties

Delegated act	Non-legislative and legally binding	European Commission	A legislative act may delegate to the Commission the power to adopt non-legislative acts of general application to supplement or amend certain non-essential elements of the legislative act (Article 290 TFEU)
Implementing act	Non-legislative and legally binding	European Commission	An implementing act is a legally binding act that sets conditions to ensure that EU laws are applied uniformly (Article 291 TFEU)

Article 191 TFEU recommends that ‘harmonisation measures’ adopted by the EU legislators to protect the environment include “a safeguard clause allowing Member States to take provisional measures, for non-economic environmental reasons” (para. 2(2)). In other words, EU environmental laws should aim to adopt minimum measures rather than to regulate the field extensively. This is also in line with the principle of subsidiarity (Article 5(3) TEU). As a result, Member States have been generally left with a large freedom in the choice of measures to implement EU law and the extent of the protection offered in their territory. This has led to a quite scattered and fragmented legal landscape between the Member States (Squintani, 2022).

There is at EU level a rapid and significant evolution in environmental policymaking in terms of both ambition and practice. From its very beginnings, EU environmental law had adopted an approach of minimum harmonisation. This meant that the EU legislators aimed at establishing a basis for environmental protection throughout the EU while leaving Member States in charge of implementing those minimum rules into national legislation. In addition, Member States were granted powers to adopt more protective measures. For this reason, most EU environmental laws adopted since the 1970s have taken the form of directives.

In the recent decade, however, there has been a shift in the environmental policymaking approach of the EU. Increasingly, the EU legislators are adopting Regulations instead of Directives in environmental law. Some have been proposed by the European Commission as new legislation (such as the Proposal for a Regulation on Nature Restoration, COM(2022) 304 final), while others are meant to replace existing directives (e.g. the Batteries Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 replaced the Batteries Directive 2006/66/EC). Because regulations are directly applicable, they achieve higher legal harmonisation, but also limit the margin of discretion of Member States.

Another approach for regulating environmental protection has been to use another legal basis, namely Article 114 TFEU. This provision gives competence to the EU to adopt EU legislation as a way to harmonise certain concepts across all EU Member States’ legislations to ensure the well-functioning of the EU internal market (also referred to as ‘approximation of laws’). A number of environmental-related policies have been adopted using this legal basis, such as the Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH). Article 114 TFEU would typically be used as legal basis for the adoption of a Regulation, whereas Article 191 would more usually lead to the adoption of a Directive.

2.2. Environmental compliance assurance

2.2.1. The responsibility of complying with EU environmental law

The Member States have the primary responsibility for transposing, applying and implementing EU law correctly (Article 4(3) TEU; Articles 288(3) and 291(1) TFEU). The implementation of EU environmental law is typically done through 1) transposition into national rules (to give effect to EU directives), 2) fulfilment of administrative tasks, and 3) compliance on the ground by natural and legal persons (such as companies) (European Commission, 2017). This multilevel implementation is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The levels of implementation of EU environmental law. Source: based on European Commission (2017).

The European Commission is the executive arm of the EU and is notably responsible for ensuring and overseeing the application of EU law (Article 17(1) TEU). There are several ways that the European Commission can assist Member States in implementing EU law as well as ensuring that they apply it correctly. This includes dialogue and capacity building as well as sanctions and infringement procedures.

In its 2016 Communication on EU law: *Better Results through better application*, the European Commission put forward the need for measures to facilitate access to justice and support to environmental compliance assurance in Member States. The measures include high-level bilateral meetings between the European Commission and Member States to discuss compliance, capacity-building, such as exchange of best practices, and improving the quality of law-making and revising existing laws to ensure legislation is clear and accessible. The European Commission also asserts the importance of complaints as an important means of detecting infringements of EU law.

If a Member States has not correctly incorporated a directive into national law or applied EU law correctly within a certain deadline, the European Commission can take legal actions to ensure proper implementation (Article 258 TFEU). The European Commission tends to focus its enforcement efforts on systemic breaches of environmental law (European Commission, 2016; Eliantonio, 2023). In addition, the TFEU includes provisions on financial sanctions for lack of transposition of directives into national law (Article 260(3) TFEU).

2.2.2. Compliance promotion, monitoring and enforcement

The concept of environmental compliance assurance (ECA) emanates from the EU. The European Commission defines ECA as “the range of interventions used by public authorities to ensure compliance by duty-holders with environmental rules that apply to economic and other activities that directly affect the environment” (European Commission, 2017). Although most environmental legislation in Europe is adopted at EU level, the responsibility for fully and correctly implementing EU rules falls with the Member States. In practice Member States appoint public authorities at national or local level to carry out and oversee the implementation activities described above. ECA is a mechanism that aims to support Member States in complying with EU environmental legislation (European Commission, 2017).

Non-compliance is not necessarily the result of unwillingness or criminality, but may also result from confusion, poor understanding or lack of investment. Nevertheless, the impacts of non-compliance on the environment, human health and the economy are highly problematic even if they vary in nature, scale and persistence. That is why mechanisms for securing compliance are crucial.

In practice, Member States may use three broad types of intervention (European Commission, 2018; see also Figure 3), which are collectively referred to as ECA, namely compliance promotion, compliance monitoring and compliance enforcement (see also D3.1 (Wehn and Pfeiffer, 2024) for more specification about this):

- Compliance *promotion* refers to the efforts Member States shall deploy in supporting duty-holders in abiding by the rules established in EU law. This may include providing information, identifying the need for specific skills training, facilitating the sharing of good practices, etc. The purpose is to prevent and limit the cases of non-compliance that are the result of lack of information or ability.
- Compliance *monitoring* consists of ensuring good compliance with the rules. Activities of inspection, investigation by the police or examinations of complaints by the public are examples of activities carried out for monitoring. This is a phase that is diagnostic in that it aims to identify potential problems.
- Compliance *enforcement* comes when non-compliance has been detected and aims to correct the situation and obtain redress. Enforcement may take the form of e.g. warnings, remedial measures or sanctions, and require administrative, civil or criminal proceedings. This type of intervention is corrective in that it seeks to change a situation of non-compliance.

Figure 3. The three types of ECA intervention. Source: European Commission (2017).

Table 2 below shows three different definitions found 1) on the website of the European Commission, 2) in the 2018 Commission communication on environmental compliance and governance, and 3) in the more4nature DoA. These definitions are largely similar, but each also offer useful precisions of how to understand the three types of ECA interventions.

Table 2. Definitions of the three types of ECA interventions.

Source	Compliance promotion	Compliance monitoring	Compliance enforcement
Webpage of the European Commission: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/law-and-governance/compliance-assurance_en	Promote means helping businesses and other duty-holders to comply through means such as awareness-raising, guidance, ‘frequently asked questions’ and helpdesks. This represents the ‘preventive’ part of compliance assurance.	Monitor means detecting and assessing non-compliance and providing solid evidence for enforcement. It covers inspections, police investigations, examination of complaints from the public. This represents the ‘diagnostic’ part of compliance assurance.	Enforce means stopping those who disregard the rules, sanctioning them and obliging them to rectify the damage. It covers, amongst other things, official warnings, cease-and-desist orders, administrative or criminal proceedings, application of sanctions, and demands to take remedial action. These represent the ‘corrective’ part of compliance assurance.
Commission Communication, EU actions to	Compliance promotion helps duty-holders to	Compliance monitoring identifies and characterises	Follow-up and enforcement draw on administrative, criminal

improve environmental compliance and governance, COM(2018)100.pdf	comply through means such as guidance, 'frequently asked questions' and help-desks.	duty-holder conduct and detects and assesses any non-compliance, using environmental inspections and other checks.	and civil law to stop, deter, sanction and obtain redress for non-compliant conduct and encourage compliance.
more4nature project proposal (DoA)	Compliance promotion includes the range of actions that authorities undertake to help businesses and individuals meet their obligations, and to prevent or reduce infringements and the harm that they cause. Actions include providing information and advice on how to comply and trying to 'crimeproof' legislation, i.e. designing obligations in a manner that deters infringements from occurring.	Compliance monitoring includes all forms of inspection, surveillance and investigation that may be undertaken to verify compliance or discover and characterise infringements.	Follow-up and enforcement involves actions by a competent authority to respond to infringements detected. Effective responses are necessary in order to punish, deter, and remediate damage. Responses may include administrative, civil and criminal law enforcement.

It should be noted that ECA is not directly synonymous to general compliance, which is a broader term encompassing also ECA. The European Commission's policy on ECA is targeted at Member States with the particular aim of cooperating with and supporting their efforts to ensure that national authorities promote, check and enforce compliance with EU environmental laws in an effective way (European Commission website). Likewise, the terms 'promotion', 'monitoring' and 'enforcement' as they are used in this report refer to the definitions above, not to a broader understanding with which these terms may otherwise be associated.

2.2.3. The (national) actors of ECA

The authorities responsible for carrying out the various ECA interventions at the national level will vary depending on the task at hand: some may have raising-awareness roles, some may collect data, some may exercise audits, and some may investigate and prosecute (European Commission, 2018). The level of coercion they can exercise thus varies as well. Authorities promoting compliance would generally focus on providing information and other forms of technical assistance to duty-holders. On the other hand, some monitoring activities may require more forceful measures, such as imposing in-site inspections. As for enforcement activities, they may be carried by the police officers that may have recourse to physical force or arrest offenders.

Thus, the role of non-state actors in supporting and cooperating with or against national authorities carrying out ECA, which is the focus of the more4nature project, must be carefully thought through from a legal and ethical perspective. We refer to more4nature D3.1 for a more elaborate discussion on the matter.

2.3. Citizen science, citizen generated data and citizen actions

The more4nature project aims to include citizens and communities as key actors in ECA. Within the broad denomination of ‘citizen science’, the project focuses on two types of citizen involvement, namely ‘citizen generated data’ (CGD) and ‘citizen & community-led actions’ (CCLA). In line with the Deliverable D3.1 – Methodology for Double Loop Action Research (Wehn and Pfeiffer, 2024), this section provides definitions of these concepts and their understanding in the context of this report.

2.3.1. Citizen science

Citizen science (CS) is broadly understood as involving civilian actors in various forms of collaborative data collection and knowledge generation, contributing to both local and global environmental challenges (Fritz et al., 2019; Haklay et al., 2021). It is a multi-stakeholder as well as a multi-dimensional phenomenon (Hager et al., 2021; Wehn, 2022). According to Kragh et al. (2023) “citizen science encompasses a diverse range of interdisciplinary methods to tap into the collective intelligence of the general public from collecting data to involving the public more broadly in research design, resource management, and decision-making.” It can take various forms (e.g. science-driven contributory initiatives; community-based monitoring schemes; citizen observatories with close links to policy and decision makers) and present innovative ways of generating knowledge at the local level (Wehn et al. 2021).

According to McKinley et al. (2017), citizen science shall be seen as a rigorous process of scientific discovery, indistinguishable from conventional science apart from the participation of volunteers. Indeed, when properly designed, carried out, and evaluated, CS can provide sound science, efficiently generate high-quality data, and help solve problems. In addition, it may even empower citizens in sustainable natural resource management - cognitively, politically, socially and economically (Danielsen et al. 2021), contributing to conflict resolution and strengthening self-determination (Johnson et al. 2021).

CS initiatives span from those primarily focused on CGD and knowledge co-creation, to those directed towards actions e.g. such as conservation actions. Yet, data collection is considered a core activity of any form of CS (Haklay et al., 2021). Additionally, CS is a multi-stakeholder and multi-dimensional phenomenon (Hager et al., 2021; Wehn, 2022). CS initiatives, whether focused on generating data or promoting environmental stewardship and protection, hold significant relevance for ECA. For more details on CS and its role within the ECA framework, please refer to the more4nature methodology outlined in D3.1 (Wehn and Pfeiffer, 2024).

2.3.2. Citizen & community-led actions

Citizen & community-led actions (CCLA) is not a term commonly used in the existing literature where one may find other denominations, including citizen initiatives (Igalla et al. 2019), social enterprises (Cheng 2015; Teasdale 2012), self-organisation (Anttila and Stern 2005; Van Meerkerk et al. 2013), and grassroots initiatives (Ornetzeder and Rohrer 2013). Igalla et al. (2019) define ‘citizen initiatives’, perhaps the most widely used of these terms, as “a form of self-

organisation in which citizens mobilize energy and resources to collectively define and carry out projects aimed at providing public goods or services for their community”. This definition incorporates elements of ‘volunteerism’ and ‘civil society’, as citizens come together to attend to community needs. The concepts of ‘civil society’ and ‘volunteer’ organizations are thus closely tied to community-driven actions.

In the more4nature project, the term ‘citizen & community-led actions’ (CCLA) is used not as a synonym to those other denominations but refers to actions that citizens and communities can take to improve environmental protection. CCLA may also joining forces with existing organisations, networks and initiatives, including FabLabs and LivingLabs, to implement, or even co-design such actions from scratch (see D3.1). The concept is meant to evolve throughout the project based on findings and experience from the partners. In this report, CCLA and the types of activities this term covers in relation to ECA are understood in line with the more4nature methodology presented in D3.1 (Wehn and Pfeiffer, 2024).

CCLA is defined in D3.1 (Wehn and Pfeiffer, 2024) as “actions and interventions for improving the implementation of environmental rules on the ground, related to the three pillars of ECA, taken or initiated by individual citizens, civil society organizations or communities”. The actions include e.g. engaging with authorities to ensure enforcement of set targets or change of inadequate policies, engaging with duty-holders to encourage their compliance with targets, engaging with authorities to ensure enforcement of set targets or change of inadequate policies, or taking legal action against wrongdoers (see Figure 4).

Compliance is good - keep it going!			Both options possible		Compliance is NOT good				
Engage entities with environmental impact to encourage compliance to targets	Engage authorities to enforce set targets	<i>Celebrate!</i> 	Engage authorities to change or create policy/regulation (supra or national level)	Engage with media to generate attention about the topic	Abstain from action because advised not to do so (e.g. dangerous)	(radical) Activist action	Take solution-driven practical action	Encourage responsible authority/policy maker to reassess the monitoring framework	Take legal action (or require authorities to do so)

Figure 4. Conceptualisation of ‘citizen & community-led actions’ developed by T3.1. Source: Miro board - Scoping more4nature focus in the policy cycle (2024).

2.3.3. Citizen generated data

Citizen science actions may lead citizens to generate data. According to Fritz et al. (2019), citizen generated data (CGD) can be characterized according to five main dimensions: space, time, theme, process and data management. The authors establish that there is a clear value for the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), i.e. the focus of their study, to use CGD. Such data, often produce in real or near-real time, hold the potential to provide a more precise and robust representation of progress towards the SDGs (Borghys et al., 2024). Because CGD is rooted in local contexts, they contribute to amplifying citizen voices and to include those typically marginalised and hard-to-reach populations. The production and utilisation of CGD fosters the direct, active and invested participation of individuals in advancing environmental protection (e.g. Moczek et al., 2021).

With the proliferation of sources of data collection, such as sensors, satellites, drones, online platforms, mobile phones and numerous other digital devices and infrastructures, the production of data by citizens or communities has been fast increasing (Lämmerhirt et al. 2018), and it is undoubtedly a source of data to reckon with in ECA. There is a major barrier to the use of CGD that is linked to the uncertainty regarding the quality of the data (Fritz et al., 2019). However, there are ways of evaluating the quality of such data, using quality-assurance methods (Kosmala et al., 2016).

Together, CCLA and CGD provide great opportunities for promoting policy compliance in innovative ways through joint data collection and knowledge production and empower citizens in sustainable natural resource management. However, the use of these tools in ECA is not easy in practice. CCLA are often hampered by a lack of capacity and common methodologies, whereas CGD suffer from a lack of institutionalised/official avenues for citizens to submit data to relevant authorities, uncertainty about whether they could or will be used and from a lack of trust in the data collected. Exploring and demonstrating how these barriers and obstacles can be overcome is the main aim of the more4nature project.

2.4. Horizontal and thematic policy areas

The more4nature project focuses on the role of CCLA and CGD in enhancing ECA in the Z/B/D policy areas. The policies selected for the analysis in this report are thus all related to one or more of those areas. Some policies specifically aim to contribute to the objectives of one or more policy areas (e.g. zero pollution), whereas other policies are cross-cutting (see Table 3 below for a full overview of selected policies). These cross-cutting or horizontal policies establish principles and obligations that apply to all the thematic policies. In line with the *lex specialis* doctrine, however, when there is a conflict between a general law and a more specific law, the more specific law takes precedence and should be applied over the general law (Lindroos, 2005; see also e.g. Opinion of Advocate General in Case C-285/06, point 72; and Joined Cases C-421/00, C-426/00 and C-16/01 *Sterbenz and Hang* [2003] ECR I-1007, point 48). Figure 5 illustrates the interaction between horizontal and vertical policies.

Figure 5. Interaction between horizontal (cross-cutting) and vertical (thematic) policies. Source: the authors.

2.4.1. Horizontal (cross-cutting) policies on compliance

Some environmental policies are ‘horizontal’ (or cross-cutting), in the sense that they do not target a specific environmental threat (like pollution) or topic (like biodiversity), but they establish the basis for good policymaking and policy compliance (i.e. transparent, participatory, accountable). Horizontal policies have an administrative nature in the sense that they primarily deal with the procedural aspects of environmental governance rather than setting specific substantive environmental standards or targets, and theoretically then are applied in all environmental

policies henceforth (Newig and Fritsch, 2009; Lee and Abbott, 2003). Horizontal policies form the baseline for engaging the public and civil society in compliance promotion, monitoring and enforcement.

For ensuring the effectiveness of environmental policies, and thus of environmental protection, a number of preconditions must be in place. *Access to information* on the environment is indispensable for enabling the public and the private sector to making environmentally sound decisions. Access to information fosters transparency, which is essential for an open and democratic governance system. Sound environmental decisions must be grounded in scientific evidence and reliable data and it is thus essential that decision-makers are aware of the full range of environmental impacts associated with their actions and can make informed choices based on objective data rather than political, economic, or short-term interests. Information also allows stakeholders and rightsholders, citizens, NGOs and local communities, to participate in decision-making processes. Successful compliance promotion is largely dependent on a good information flow, and effective compliance monitoring requires access to the relevant information.

Another precondition is *public participation* that plays a critical role in shaping, implementing and sustaining policies. It allows local and experiential knowledge held by the public – that may not be otherwise available – to be provided to decision-makers, fosters a sense of ownership over environmental policies and increases the likelihood of achieving voluntary compliance (O’Faircheallaigh, 2010; Dietz, Ostrom and Stern, 2003). By involving citizens, communities, and civil society organizations in decision-making processes, public participation contribute to boosting the legitimacy of environmental policies. Policies that are developed with public participation tend to have greater social acceptance (Connelly and Richardson, 2005). Generally, collaborative processes, where stakeholders work together to find solutions, can lead to compromises that satisfy a broader range of interests. Some also argue that public participation can help build more resilient institutions capable of addressing complex and evolving environmental challenges.

Finally, *access to justice* contributes to ensuring that environmental laws are enforceable, that wrongdoers are held accountable, and that communities have the power to defend their environmental rights. Without it, environmental laws and policies could be undermined, reducing their effectiveness in protecting the environment. Access to justice is essential for ensuring that environmental regulations are not merely symbolic but actively enforced. By providing avenues for legal recourse, access to justice empowers citizens and civil society to take an active role in the enforcement of environmental laws. This democratizes environmental governance, allowing individuals and organizations to serve as watchdogs and enforcers of environmental protections. Krämer (2009) points out that access to justice shifts some enforcement responsibilities from the state to the public, increasing societal oversight over environmental decisions. It also promotes transparency, fairness, and equity in environmental governance, further strengthening compliance with environmental laws. Citizens and other representative of the civil society should also be protected in the exercise of their right to access to justice or in providing evidence or serving as witnesses in legal proceedings.

The Aarhus Convention – adopted in 1998 and ratified by the EU in 2005 – establishes a framework that empowers the public to participate in environmental decision-making, access environmental information, and seek justice in environmental matters. These principles enhance transparency, accountability, and public oversight, which are essential for ensuring that environmental laws and regulations are properly implemented and enforced. The Convention is implemented in EU law through the Aarhus Regulation (EC) No 1367/2006. In addition, the EU legal framework provides significant avenues for public access to environmental information and participation in environmental decision-making. Central to this is Directive 2003/4/EC on public access to environmental information. This directive gives citizens and organizations the right to

access environmental information held by public authorities. Moreover, Directive 2003/35/EC establishes public participation provisions related to certain environmental matters, reinforcing the right to engage in decision-making processes.

The Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) process helps ensure that potential environmental impacts of proposed projects are identified, assessed, and mitigated before approval, promoting compliance with both specific EU directives and broader environmental principles. The EIA Directive (2011/92/EU) works alongside the Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) Directive (2001/42/EC), which requires an environmental assessment for certain plans and programs. Together, these directives ensure that both individual projects and broader plans comply with EU law by systematically considering environmental impacts in line with EU environmental objectives. These policies are listed in Table 3 (overview of policies analysed in this report) and in Annex 6.1 (overview of policies identified as relevant for the more4nature project).

In terms of access to justice, there are also redress mechanisms provided by the TFEU that form further building blocks of the EU system of judicial review. On the one hand, Article 263(4) TFEU enables legal and natural persons to institute proceedings directly before the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) against acts of direct and individual concern to them, and against regulatory acts of direct concern to them that do not entail implementing measures. On the other hand, Article 267 TFEU provides the possibility for natural and legal persons to bring a case before national courts and seek to have the latter make a referral to the CJEU to decide on the validity of an EU act (EU Parliament Briefing, 2022; Milieu, 2019). Figure 6 shows the main features of the three redress mechanisms that can provide (directly or indirectly) access to justice in environmental matters.

Figure 6. Key features of the three main redress mechanisms impacting effectiveness. Inspired by Milieu (2019).

The CJEU has been pivotal in interpreting and enforcing these rights. The right of access to environmental information by the public has been at the centre of numerous cases, with the CJEU often ruling against restrictive interpretations of this right. For example, in *ClientEarth v*

European Commission (T-545/11, 2015), the CJEU General Court ruled against the European Commission, who had refused access, citing the need to protect decision-making processes. The court emphasised that transparency is essential, particularly when environmental matters are involved, and that exceptions to public access must be clearly justified. The CJEU has consistently interpreted EU law in favour of strengthening public participation in environmental decision-making. Several cases clarify aspects of how public participation should be implemented in compliance with EU directives, such as the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Directive (2011/92/EU) and the Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) Directive (2001/42/EC). In *Križan and Others* (C-416/10, 2013), the court ruled that the public must be able to participate effectively at various stages of the decision-making process, including post-decision modifications that may have environmental impacts. Importantly, it also stressed that national laws cannot unduly restrict the public's right to participate. In *Altrip* (C-72/12, 2013), the ruling required national courts to annul decisions if serious procedural flaws (such as insufficient public participation) were found.

In addition, the EU has developed a legal framework for the prosecution and punishment of serious environmental crimes across EU Member States. The newly adopted Environmental Crime Directive (2024/1203/EU) aims to ensure that serious violations of environmental laws are effectively prosecuted and punished, and to establish a framework for cooperation among EU member states in tackling these offenses. It contributes to access to justice by providing a legal framework for the prosecution and punishment of serious environmental crimes, promoting transparency and accountability, facilitating public participation in reporting and investigating violations, and supporting effective enforcement and cross-border cooperation.

2.4.2. Vertical (thematic) policy areas

The more4nature project is structured around three core environmental themes: zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention. Each of these themes cover several environmental policy objectives and legal instruments of relevance for ECA.

Zero pollution

Pollution is detrimental to both the environment and human health. The consequences of pollution are multiple, from physical to mental diseases and premature deaths, and it is affecting in particular children, people with certain medical conditions and the elderly. In addition, pollution is one of the main drivers for the loss of biodiversity (COM(2021) 400 final). There are multiple sources of pollution, and all environmental media are affected, from air to water and soil. Pollution is also a global and cross-boundary problem that must be addressed at all levels, from the regional to the international level.

The EU has developed a zero pollution vision for 2050 where air, water and soil pollution are reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems (COM(2021) 400 final). The vision includes specific reduction targets for pollution and its impacts by 2030, and the role of citizen engagement is also highlighted in the inclusion of Living Labs for smart zero pollution. Citizens can be engaged in preventing, remedying, monitoring and reporting on pollution, and there are many examples of citizen science initiatives on air quality and plastic pollution in water (see more4nature pioneer cases)

At international level, several treaties and conventions address different forms of pollution. Among the most notable are the Paris Agreement and its parent treaty, the UNFCCC, that aim at combating climate change, the Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution, and the Basel Convention on the Control of Transboundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and their

Disposal, and the OSPAR Convention, which is a regional agreement aimed at the protection of the marine environment of the North-East Atlantic.

Combating pollution is also a means of supporting the achievement several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), notably SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-Being), SDG 13 (Climate Action), SDG 14 (Life below Water) and SDG 15 (Life on Land).

Biodiversity protection

Biodiversity is threatened by a range of different factors, including climate change and land use change. Human activities, notably farming and fishing, have led to an ongoing biodiversity loss and an accompanying loss of genetic diversity, which is often referred to as Holocene extinction, or sixth mass extinction.

The EU has a strategy of putting its biodiversity on a path to recovery by 2030. As part of the European Green Deal, the biodiversity strategy for 2030 (COM(2020) 380 final) is the EU's plan for protecting nature and reversing the degradation of ecosystems. In addition, the newly adopted Nature Restoration Regulation (also known as 'Nature Restoration Law') was adopted by the EU legislators on 24 June 2024. The Regulation sets an overarching restoration objective for the long-term recovery of nature in the EU's land and sea areas, as well as binding restoration targets for specific habitats and species. EU's oldest environmental laws, the Habitats Directive (Council Directive 92/43/EEC on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora and the Birds Directive (Directive 2009/147/EC on the conservation of wild) – also known as the 'Nature Directives', – currently form the backbone of EU biodiversity policy. Another important piece of legislation is the Invasive Alien Species Regulation (Regulation (EU) 1143/2014), which includes a set of measures to be taken across the EU in relation to invasive alien species. They are also the legal basis for Natura 2000 that is the largest coordinated network of protected areas in the world. Other recent EU strategies are worth mentioning, including the Farm to Fork Strategy (COM(2020) 381 final) and the New Deal for Pollinators (COM(2023) 35 final).

Several international agreements govern biodiversity protection and conservation efforts. The most recent, and arguably most prominent one is the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF), which was adopted in 2022 during the fifteenth meeting of the UN Biodiversity Conference of the Parties (COP 15) and is signed by 196 countries, and by the EU. It is preceded by another important Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) adopted during the Earth Summit in Rio in 1992. The CBD aims at the conservation of biodiversity, the sustainable use of its components, and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from genetic resources. It was later supplemented by two agreements, the Cartagena Protocol and Nagoya Protocol. Moreover, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES) aims to protect endangered species against over-exploitation by regulating international trade. CITES, adopted under the auspices of the International Union for Conservation of Nature, entered into force in 1975 and has currently 184 parties, including the EU.

Furthermore, SDGs 14 (Life Below Water) and 15 (Life on Land) are specifically targeting biodiversity, respectively through the conservation and sustainable use of the oceans, seas and marine resources, and the protection, restoration and promotion of the sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems and a halt to biodiversity loss.

Deforestation prevention

“The threats to the world's forests are one of the biggest sustainability challenges of our time” (European Commission, 2019). Forests give human air to breathe and capture CO₂ out of the atmosphere. They host around 80% of the biodiversity on Earth. They hold cultural, social and spiritual values, and represent a large part of the land traditionally inhabited by indigenous

peoples. Yet, forests are under increasing pressure notably because of a growing demand for agricultural land. The EU is the second largest contributor to deforestation after China and is responsible for about 19% of deforestation and forest degradation worldwide.

In 2019, the European Commission put forward a Communication on Stepping up EU Action to Protect and Restore the World's Forests (COM(2019) 352 final), which aimed at safeguarding and restoring forests worldwide. It was followed, in 2023, by the adoption of an ambitious Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 on Deforestation-free Products (EUDR) that targets one of the main objectives of the Communication, namely to ensure that EU consumption no longer contributes to global deforestation. The EUDR requires that any operator and trader on the EU market must be able to prove that the products do not originate from recently deforested land or have contributed to forest degradation. On 30 December 2024, the EUDR will be applicable and the existing Regulation (EU) No 995/2010, also known as the European Union Timber Regulation (EUTR), will be repealed.

At the international level, deforestation remains under-regulated. The framework for Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation, plus the sustainable management of forests, and the conservation and enhancement of forest carbon stocks (REDD+) was negotiated under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) to facilitate intergovernmental cooperation on forests and climate change. It was adopted in 2013 at COP 19 in Warsaw and provides methodological and financing guidance for the implementation of REDD+ activities. Moreover, SDG 15 calls for the sustainable management of forests, to combat desertification, and to halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.

3. Methodological approach

This chapter aims to establish the methodological approach we adopted in conducting the policy analysis of the obstacles and opportunities for CCLA and CGD in ECA in selected EU and international Z/B/D policies. It describes the methodological process step by step, from the preparation to the policy analysis and the data analysis. The chapter ends with some considerations about the limitations of the approach.

3.1. The step-by-step methodological process

There are many detailed individual policy evaluations undertaken by EU institutions and academia. The particular focus of Task 1.1 is to map the ECA mechanisms in the selected policies (including policy documents, amendments, and associated implementation guidelines) and then to assess these in terms of citizen science contribution in the form of CCLA and CGD. The approach adopted for conducting this policy analysis is interpretative; it maps the current policy landscape and, through a comprehensive review of policy language, seeks to identify barriers to and opportunities for promoting the use of CCLA and CGD in ECA. It does not, however, map or evaluate the actual implementation of individual policy with respect to CCLA and CGD.

The policy mapping conducted in Task 1.1 during the implementation phase of the more4nature project (i.e. during M1-6, also referred to as 'Phase 1' in this report) has been developed through three key steps, each of which includes several stages and an iterative process (as shown in Figure 7 below).

Figure 7. Step-by-step methodological process of the policy analysis. Source: the authors.

3.1.1. Step 1: Preparations

The selection of policies

A first filtering of the policies relevant to the three areas covered by the project, namely zero pollution (Z), biodiversity protection (B) and deforestation prevention (D), as well as to public

participation and access to information, uncovered over 90 policies at international and EU level (see the full list in Annex 6.1). The policies were identified through a search of the European Commission's webpages dedicated to these thematic areas. The webpages list EU and international policies relevant for the EU. The policies identified included international treaties and conventions, UN strategies and declarations as well as EU directives and regulations, and Commission communications (sometimes referred to as actions plans, strategies and initiatives). The list was shared with all the more4nature partners for comments and suggestions.

From this initial list, it was decided to keep the policies directly identified by the pioneer cases of the more4nature project as specifically relevant. Thus, some Z/B/D policies were not selected for analysis in this report, such as the Basel Convention, Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES), Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution and the UNFCCC. However, we aim to analyse them in Phase 2 of Task 1.1. Again, all the project partners were invited to comment and make suggestions for change, and we included some policies that were not mentioned in the more4nature DoA on that basis. This is the case of the Bathing Water Directive.

The next step consisted of categorizing the identified policies in light of their binding nature, i.e. legally binding (or hard law) legal instrument on the one hand, including EU directives and regulation, and MEAs; and non-legally binding (or soft law) instruments on the other. The latter includes policy instruments such as communications and strategies from the European Commission, COP decisions and other declarations from United Nations bodies (see Annex 6.1). The choice was made to narrow the policy analysis in this deliverable to primarily look at hard law instruments. It was also decided to include the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, although it is a non-legally binding international instrument, because it provides global goals and targets to guide actions by signatory countries.

Following these steps, the list of selected policies was narrowed down even further. The choice was made to focus, in this report, on policies that were already adopted, that were not in a process of revision, and that were particularly relevant for the pioneer cases. This is why, at this stage, proposed legislation as well as policies about climate (i.e. not directly relevant to zero pollution), such as the Paris Agreement, were excluded. We also decided in this report to analyse the Aarhus Convention, but not the EU Aarhus Regulation, which implements the first, because the two are almost identical. Table 2 below compiles the final list of selected policies. These policies, 20 in total (including 16 at EU level) are presented in Table 3 below. The policies are classified first by theme (B, D, Z, Z/B and other) and then by date of adoption. This classification is kept throughout the report in Tables 6-9. The choice of classifying by theme first was made to facilitate the reading of this report by partners in charge of case studies.

Table 3. Overview of the policies selected for Phase 1 of the policy analysis.

Thematic area	Date of adoption	Name of policy	Level
Horizontal (cross-cutting) policies			
H	1998	Convention on access to information, public participation in decision-making and access to justice in environmental matters (Aarhus Convention)	UNECE
H	2001	Directive 2001/42/EC on the assessment of the effects of certain plans and programmes on the environment (Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive)*	EU
H	2003	Directive 2003/4/EC on public access to environmental information and repealing Council Directive 90/313/EEC (Public Access to Environmental Information Directive)	EU
H	2014 (codification)	Directive 2011/92/EU on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment (Environmental Impact Assessment Directive)	EU
H	2024	Directive (EU) 2024/1203 on the protection of the environment through criminal law and replacing Directives 2008/99/EC and 2009/123/EC (Environmental Crime Directive)	EU
Vertical (thematic) policies			
B	1992	Council Directive 92/43/EEC on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora (Habitats Directive)	EU
B	1992	Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)	UN
B	2009 (codification)	Directive 2009/147/EC on the conservation of wild birds (Birds Directive)*	EU
B	2014	Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014 on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species (Invasive Alien Species Regulation)	EU
B	2022	Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF)	UNEP
D	2005	Council Regulation (EC) No 2173/2005 on the establishment of a FLEGT licensing scheme for imports of timber into the European Community (FLEGT Regulation)	EU
D	2023	Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 on the making available on the Union market and the export from the Union of certain commodities and products associated with deforestation and forest degradation and repealing Regulation	EU

		(EU) No 995/2010 (Regulation on Deforestation-free products, EUDR)	
Z	1991	Council Directive 91/676/EEC of 12 December 1991 concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources (Nitrates Directive)	EU
Z	1992	Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (OSPAR Convention)	Regional
Z	2006	Directive 2006/7/EC concerning the management of bathing water quality and repealing Directive 76/160/EEC (Bathing Water Directive)	EU
Z	2016	Directive 2016/2284/EU on the reduction of national emissions of certain atmospheric pollutants (National Emission reduction Commitments Directive / NEC Directive)*	EU
Z	2019	Directive (EU) 2019/904 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment (Single-Use Plastics Directive / SUP Directive)*	EU
B/Z	2000	Directive 2000/60/EC establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy (Water Framework Directive)	EU
B/Z	2008	Directive 2008/56/EC establishing a framework for community action in the field of marine environmental policy (Marine Strategy Framework Directive, MSFD)	EU
B/D/Z	2024	Regulation (EU) 2024/1991 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 June 2024 on nature restoration and amending Regulation (EU) 2022/869 (Nature Restoration Regulation)	EU

* For these policies, in addition to main text of the policy, we also assessed associated guidance documents and implementing instructions (where relevant).

B = Biodiversity protection; D = Deforestation prevention; Z = Zero pollution; H = Horizontal

The selection of criteria and keywords

To structure and optimise the analysis of the selected policies, we decided to identify policy criteria for which policies to conduct assess. We also identified keywords to use in those assessments. The choice of the policy criteria related to the different types of ECA interventions, the authorities in charge of compliance and the two dimensions of citizen science analysed, namely CCLA and CGD. In addition, cross-referencing of policies related to ECA was also selected as a policy criterion. The selection of keywords was meant to be used as an entry point to the policy, but the whole document (and any accompanying documents) was eventually read in full by the researcher who conducted the policy analysis.

In a first step, we read selected literature on citizen science for environmental compliance jointly identified and suggested by project partners. We looked at different approaches to the potential inclusion of citizen science initiatives in ECA as well as the variety of terms used to discuss aspects of citizen science and of environmental compliance. For example, an article by Fraisl et al. (2020)

presents the SDG indicator framework consisting of 244 SDG indicators and identifies “past and ongoing citizen science initiatives that could directly or indirectly provide data for these indicators”. The authors use terms such as ‘public participation’, ‘voluntary contributions’, and ‘knowledge production’, which were extracted and used to start compiling a list of relevant search keywords for each of the policy aspect, i.e.

- Compliance promotion
- Compliance monitoring
- Compliance enforcement
- CA in compliance promotion
- CGD in compliance monitoring
- CA in compliance enforcement
- CGD in compliance enforcement

An article by Danielsen et al. (2014) examines the indicators of 12 international environmental agreements, including the CBD, to develop a framework for assessing the potential for citizen science. From this, keywords were extracted such as ‘local stakeholders’ and ‘community-based monitoring’. Danielsen et al. (2023) also apply this framework to assess the potential for involving citizens in monitoring the Kunming Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF). This article provided further relevant terms, including ‘co-creation of knowledge’, ‘indigenous peoples’, ‘citizen scientists’ and ‘public engagement’.

The first selection of keywords was suggested based on literature and previous knowledge. This was an iterative process, where we suggested a set of words that could indicate a role for citizens in promotion, monitoring and enforcement, such as “citizen, community, engagement”. On the other hand – looking for constraints, we also included words such as “technical, sensor, expert”. We also included general key words related to the aspects we are assessing, such as “data, enforcement, compliance”. After having compiled a list of relevant keywords (or concepts) for each policy aspect, we submitted those to the project partners for feedback. The partners, who have extended experience in the field of citizen science provided invaluable contribution, suggesting specific words that could indicate the inclusion or constraint of citizen participation as well as sharing insights about how some elements of language in the law can be interpreted by Member States in implementing EU law (e.g. requirements about data ‘quality’ may be used to restrict the use of CGD).

Next, we started searching through some of the selected policies using the lists of keywords as an entry point to identify the different types of interventions of ECA as well as a possible contribution or restriction to the use of CGD or CCLA in ECA. While conducting the search, some keywords were added to the initial lists as they were identified in the policy documents, whereas some keywords (such as ‘barefoot lawyers’ and ‘grassroot initiatives’) were removed when it appeared clearly that they would not be found in policy documents. The identification of keywords in a policy was used to pinpoint provisions or paragraphs that were particularly relevant for our analysis. However, there is not necessarily a one-to-one relationship between indicating citizen science in the policy document and the actual room for citizen science. The lists of keywords that were eventually agreed upon are presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4. Keywords for policy analysis developed by more4nature partners.

Focus	Compliance promotion	Compliance monitoring	Compliance enforcement
General	access action assist* availab* awar* campaign communicat* compl* cooperat* disseminat* emission guid* incentiv* inform* infrastructure integr* measur* notif* particip* prevent* promot* tool*	access action assess* audit* collect* compl* inspect* investigat* monitor* observ* report* study surve* track* verif*	action administrative charges civil compl* correct* criminal enforc* fail* fee/s infring* injunction interim (measures) judg* law legal penalt* prohibit* prosecut* sanction* shortcoming violate*
Authorities in charge	authorit* bod* (body/ies) contact* (point) institution* member States third party	authorit* bod* (body/ies) contact* (point) institution* member States ythird party	authorit* bod* (body/ies) contact* (point) institution* member States third party
Citizen & community-led actions (CCLA)	access* advocacy anticipation aware* campaign* citizen co-creation communit* contribut* cooperat* disseminat* influence inform* initiative lobby* on behalf of particip* petition	N/A	advocacy anticipat* aware* campaigns citizen co* (co-creation, co-production) communit* disseminat* influence inform* initiative* lobby* on behalf of petition public science self*

	public qualified science self* social enterprises transparen* warning		social transparen* warning
Citizen generated data (CGD)	N/A	access* bottom-up citizen co* (co-production; co- creation) collaborative collection communit* consult* crowdsourcing data disseminat* engag* experience indigenous initiative* know* local manage* participat* public quality scien* (scientific; science) sensor stakeholders standards technical transparen* user	access citizen co* (co-created, co- production) collaborative collection collegial (projects) communicat* communit* complain* contractual contribut* Court Data enforce* initiatives interest* judg* justice lawsuit legitimate method* public scien* (scientific; science) source standard* technical transparen*

The development of the template

To conduct the analysis of each policy in a coherent and uniform manner, a template document (Annex 6.1) was developed, partly inspired by a template developed by NIVA as part of the Horizon Europe ‘CrossGov’ project² for the purpose of mapping policy coherence across EU policies link to the European Green Deal (EGD). From the CrossGov template we kept the first two steps:

- **Step 1.1** consisting in the identification of the persons carrying out the review;

² [Home - Crossgov Project](#)

- **Step 1.2** entailing the identification of the details of the policy (including notably aims, targets and key dates).

For the next steps, we developed our own approach in line with the objectives of the more4nature project. Three steps were hence created that looked at different aspects of the policy analysis:

- **Step 1.3** is dedicated to ECA in general, i.e. with promotion, monitoring and enforcement analysed each on their own without the lens of CCLA or CGD;
- **Step 1.4** narrows down to stakeholders' involvement in the three stages of ECA. For promotion the focus was CCLA, whereas for monitoring it was CGD. For enforcement, we looked first at CCLA, and then at CGD;
- **Step 1.5** is concerned with cross-cutting coherence, i.e. whether the policy being analysed referred to other policies with regards to compliance, including in particular issues of access to information, public participation or access to justice.

For each of these steps, we point to the keywords identified previously (see section 'selection of criteria and keywords' above). The combination of keywords is different for each aspect, but some keywords (such as compliance, transparency, citizens) are used in multiple aspects. The keywords are meant to help identify the relevant aspects of the policy in question.

In **Step 1.3**, for each of the ECA stages, two main questions are asked:

1. What does the policy seem to say (if anything) about compliance promotion/monitoring/enforcement?
2. Which, if any, authority/ies does the policy put in charge of promotion/monitoring/enforcement?

Each of these questions should be answered using the relevant keywords, but not exclusively, and clear references added (including provision in the policy and extracts of text). In addition, the researcher in charge of each policy should write their own assessment for the first question, and a short explanation (including the level at which compliance is to take place and identification of the authorities) for the second question.

In **Step 1.4**, there are two questions to be answered:

1. What does the policy seem to say (if anything) about CA/CGD in compliance promotion/monitoring/enforcement?
2. Does the policy seem to indicate that CA/CGD in compliance promotion/monitoring/enforcement is restricted, and if so, how?

As for the previous step, using relevant keywords, the researcher shall include specific references and extract of text, in addition to writing an assessment. For the second question, the researchers asked to select yes/no before moving on to justifying that answer.

The template development process was iterative and the template was revised several times during the Phase 1 of the policy analysis, either to add or remove keywords, or to adjust the questions for each step. Four researchers (from NIVA) were involved in the initial analysis, and they all fed in suggestions to modify the template based on the policies they were in charge of. This iterative process allowed us to learn from our experience with conducting the policy analysis and ensure that the template could be used by a wider set of users with a larger sample of policy documents, thus improving the template and the analysis itself.

3.1.2. Step 2: Document analysis

Data collection and initial document analysis

Policies in the subsample were divided among one of the four NIVA researchers, each of whom was then responsible for carrying out the document analysis, based on the guidance laid out in the template, and summarized in Figure 8 below.

In **Step 2.1**, metadata regarding the policy (policy name, year, additional guidance documents, written aims or objectives, updates and amendments, and explicit mention of international conventions of relevance) was collected into the template.

In **Step 2.2**, we filled the template with specific provisions or articles (copied and pasted from the policy and into the template) that demonstrated how policy makers intend to address certain policy design aspects, including: 1) the three types of ECA interventions broadly, 2) the extent to which CGD or CCLA appears implicitly or explicitly encouraged or prohibited within each aspect, 3) cross-referencing of policies. To do so, the researcher searched within the policy document itself (as well as in any linked official guidance³) using the keywords (e.g., monitor, citizen, justice) input into text search functions (e.g., ctrl+f or MultiFind).

For each keyword search, the paragraphs containing the text from that search was screened for inclusion based on the questions in in the template (presented above) and entered into the template in the appropriate section(s). Preambulatory text was screened last, as it is further elaborated on in the articles. Keywords that yielded relevant results were noted in the template whereby occurrences of words that did not relate to either ECA, or CCLA and CGD were dismissed. After all relevant text was inserted into each section of the template, the researcher had a compilation of all articles and provisions that were relevant for the policy design aspects.

For each policy, this process took between four and six hours and allowed the researcher to become familiar with the policy itself, and therefore was able to assess it.

Next, in **Step 2.3**, the researcher used qualitative methods to summarize and assess both a) the overall approach prescribed by the policy document to ensure policy compliance, and b) the extent to which this approach facilitated, explicitly included, discouraged, or prohibited involvement of and engagement with CCLA and CGD.

From here, the filled-out template and policy was sent to a project partner for input and a cursory review to ensure nothing was missed or mischaracterised (see ‘review process’ below).

Figure 8. Three steps for document analysis: data extraction, assessment, and peer review. Source: the authors.

During the second face-to-face (F2F) meeting of the consortium of the more4nature project on 28-30 May 2024, the leaders of Task 1.1 and Task 1.2 organised a workshop whereby four groups

³ Due to time constraints, we were not able to assess all the associated guidance documents and implementing instructions for each policy. Policies for which those documents were assessed in addition to the main text are marked with *.

of 6-7 participants were asked to analyse a policy each. The purpose of this workshop was twofold: first, it allowed more4nature partners to familiarise themselves with the template developed by Task 1.1, knowing that a similar template will be developed for and used by the partners to conduct policy analysis at the national level (i.e. as part of the more4nature case studies). Second, it confronted the partners to the difficulty of interpreting policies, especially regarding aspects that, in most cases, legislators appear not to have had in mind at the time of adoption of the policies.

The analysis was carried out during the workshop was done using a simplified template (see Annex O) and a policy text where relevant provisions were highlighted in yellow by the Task 1.1 researchers. Each group of participants had 45 minutes to go through the policy and write their assessment in the simplified template. The analysis was later incorporated into the more comprehensive template (see Annex 6.1) in accordance with Step 2 of the methodological analysis.

The four policies that were analysed at the F2F meeting were:

- The Bathing Water Directive (EU, Z)
- The Paris Agreement (International, Z) – *this policy was later excluded from this report because of its climate focus (i.e. not strictly ‘zero pollution’)*
- The Invasive Alien Species Regulation (EU, B)
- The Forest Law Enforcement, Governance and Trade (FLEGT) Regulation (EU, D)

The review process

Once the initial part of the document analysis completed, the filled template (one per policy) was sent to a project partner for review. The identification of the partner was done by the partners themselves filling in their interest and availability in a shared Excel document, or by the researcher in the initial analysis based on the known expertise of the partners.

The reviewers (i.e. the project partner in charge of the review) did not conduct the same in-depth analysis as in the initial part of the document analysis. Instead, they were asked to look more specifically at the parts of the template that pertained to the ‘assessment’ of the findings. In other words, the reviewer was expected to check that the findings of the initial researcher were in line with their own interpretation of the text of the policy and to complete the analysis where necessary.

Given time constraints, not all policies went through this review process. However, all were discussed internally by the authors of this report as explained in the section about ‘results extraction’ below. Policies that went through a review process by partners are marked with an # in the Tables 6-9 below in Chapter 4.

Upon receiving the review, the initial researcher revised the template in accordance with the comments received or suggested changes proposed. If the initial researcher did not agree or did not understand the feedback from the reviewer, a bilateral conversation took place with the aim of clarifying or nuancing the assessment.

Data extraction

Based on the finalised template, the initial researcher extracted the main findings from the document analysis and transferred the results into Tables 6-8 of this report.

3.1.3. Step 3: Data analysis

Having extracted the data from the document analysis, we proceeded to determine trends and gaps within and across the policy landscape as it relates to the encouragement or restriction of CCLA or CGD within policies, as well as to identify exemplars. This analysis was necessarily

subjective because a) definitions of CCLA and CGD within the policy context had not yet been fully developed and agreed in the more4nature project (see Deliverable 3.1), and b) we found that policies generally did not explicitly refer to CCLA and CGD. This means that we made a determination of whether and how CCLA or CGD seems to be encouraged or restricted in the context of environmental compliance promotion, monitoring and enforcement based on own reading and understanding of each policy.

Results extraction and categorisation

In order to make the analysis methodologically robust and replicable, two measures were applied:

- 1) The development of a classification framework to categorise the possibility of using citizen science in the form of CCLA or CGD in the selected policies using colour codes from green to red (see Table 5).
- 2) A consensus-based decision-making whereby the authors of this report discussed what elements should be considered to determine the colour-coding applicable based only on an analysis of the text of the policies (and guidance documents), and not on other knowledge of or experience with a particular policy.

The colour codes are defined as follows:

- **Green** means that ‘some form of CCLA or CGD is explicitly mentioned or encouraged’ in the policy text. The colour was used for compliance promotion when a policy specifically required that the public be widely provided with information and encouraged unrestricted public participation, thus allowing for two-way communication between the public authorities in charge of compliance and the public.
- **Yellow** means that there are ‘no apparent restrictions’ to the use of CCLA or CGD in the policy text, and that some form of enabling even appears to exist. This means that policies that open for one-way communication (i.e. public authorities having to provide information to the public) were classified as yellow.
- **Orange** indicates that ‘some elements of restriction’ are found in the policy text, but without clearly indicating that CCLA or CGD cannot be used for ECA. This may be because the policy requires expertise from the data provider or includes requirement about the quality of such data. Although such requirements do not necessarily exclude CGD, they lead to their use being restricted in practice or in the national legislation of implementation.
- **Red** is to be used when a policy appears based on the policy text to ‘clearly restrict’ the use of CCLA or CGD for ECA. This situation may result from a policy specifying which actors can contribute to ECA, thus excluding the public at large (and therefore citizens). In other words, no communication is possible between public authorities in charge of compliance to the public.
- An additional colour, **grey**, was added for cases in which no information was to be found in the policy about a type of ECA interventions or if the policy simply referred to Member States to establish the rules (e.g. on access to justice) without additional specifications about what the national provisions should contain. In those case, the assessment was deemed “not possible”.

It should be noted that some policies seemed to contain both opportunities and restrictions for the use of CCLA or CGD in ECA. In such cases, we discussed whether the element of restriction was problematic as such or could be justified by the nature of the policy theme (e.g. sensitive information) or the need to ensure quality of procedures (e.g. using ISO standards).

Table 5. Classification framework for categorising policies.

Green: Some form of CCLA or CGD is explicitly mentioned /encouraged (e.g. public participation). Two-way communication	Yellow: No apparent restrictions. Basic/indirect enabling of CCLA or CGD in ECA (e.g. provision of information). One-way communication	Orange: Some elements of restriction. E.g. requirements of expertise or quality that may be interpreted in a way that impedes CCLA or CGD	Red: Clearly restricted e.g. because the actors specified do not include the public. Little to no communication	Grey: No assessment possible at EU/ international level
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Applying the framework, we (the authors) discussed each policy together to determine the appropriate colour. In cases where we could not make a determination based on the assessment in the template, we collectively went back to the original policy document for additional context. Such a methodology provides structure and consistency for conducting subjective analysis so that trends and gaps can be determined, and assessment can be conducted across diverse policy documents. This analysis can be scaled and replicated to include other policy documents.

Identification of trends and preliminary findings

In order to summarise and provide an overview of the different policies, we use the colour-coding framework (see Table 5) to present our findings for all of the 20 policies analysed for this report (see Table 9). In Chapter 4, we summarise our findings across the policies for each type of ECA intervention as well as overarching takeaways. These findings are presented in this report in the same order as in the template, i.e. starting with CCLA in compliance promotion, followed by CGD in compliance monitoring, and finally CCLA and CGD in compliance enforcement. We did not separate the findings about CCLA from those about CGD in compliance enforcement, because we generally found little about compliance enforcement in the policies.

Drafting of the report

The first outline and structure of the report was provided to project partners for feedback (14 March 2024). The report writing was done in parallel with the policy analysis. This iterative process allowed us to learn by doing and improve both the policy analysis and our interpretation of it, presented as findings in Chapter 4 below.

3.2. Limitations

The policy analysis and drafting of the report took place between months 1 and 6 of the more4nature project. The timeline was therefore quite short to develop and conduct the process developed in this chapter. It was further complicated by that fact that such systematic policy mapping of whether citizen science could be used in ECA has, to our knowledge, not been conducted before. Therefore, we had to establish the basis for the analysis and define the framework for the analysis. A lot of time was spent discussing, testing and refining the methodology and the template.

In addition, given the limited selection of policies that we reviewed, our findings are necessarily only valid to the extent that they concern these particular policies. We expect our understanding of the policy field to further evolve as we prepare the next report from Task 1.1, Deliverable 1.9,

due in Month 24 of the project. Also, step 3 (data analysis) overlapped largely with step 2 (document analysis), and we had to review our findings until the last stage of the writing of this report, with limited time and capacity to discuss each of them in great depth.

4. Preliminary findings about citizen & community-led actions and citizen generated data in environmental compliance assurance

In this chapter we present the detailed examination of 20 policies and main findings from the analysis of the selected EU and international policies related to zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention (presented in Table 3 above). The policies are referred to by their short name, with thematic area (Z/B/D/other) and year of adoption in brackets. We discuss some key findings for each type of ECA intervention and present a summary of the main results from each policy in Tables 6-8 below.

When analysing policy documents to map and assess their compliance assurance mechanisms, there are several key elements to look at. These mechanisms are essentially the methods and processes put in place to ensure that the requirements of the policy or law are met.

By examining key aspects, we were able to develop an understanding of how a policy or law establishes compliance assurance mechanisms and what measures are in place to ensure that its provisions are effectively implemented and adhered to.

Such analysis also aims to highlight areas where improvements are needed or where additional oversight is necessary, as well as obstacles and opportunities for CCLA and CGD to contribute to promoting ECA processes.

4.1. The regulatory framework for environmental compliance assurance

In conducting our analysis, we found that we could identify two main categories of policies: on the one hand, there are policies that aim at achieving environmental protection in different areas, including the three areas that are the focus of the more4nature project, namely zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention (can be seen as policies with a *'vertical', thematic focus*). On the other hand, some policies have a more *horizontal approach* and, instead of targeting a specific environmental objective, they aim to contribute to broader issues of compliance with environmental legislation.

Generally, we found that the horizontal (H) policies tend to provide more opportunities for the use of CCLA or CGD in ECA than Z/B/D policies. This is largely due to the fact that horizontal policies focus on issues of governance, including the role of citizens in environmental policy, e.g. by ensuring access to document, establishing public participation in decision-making processes and guaranteeing access to justice. We did not find that horizontal policies we analysed explicitly mandate the use of citizen science, but they create a supportive framework for it. It is relevant to note that many of these policies have been adopted at a time (roughly between 1997 and 2011) when the inclusion of citizen science in ECA was not broadly discussed at policy level. The possibility of formalizing the use of citizen science initiatives in environmental compliance is recent (see e.g. European Commission, 2020)

4.2. Citizen & community-led actions in compliance promotion

The identification of a potential role for CCLA in compliance promotion is particularly intricate to establish through a policy analysis. This is because CCLA are not yet widely recognised as an approach that can contribute to ECA. Moreover, methods for ensuring compliance promotion are rarely written directly into a policy whereas monitoring and enforcement are more often specified, for example in requirements of reporting or in provisions regarding sanctions for non-compliance.

Some key points from the analysis conducted for each policy are summarised in Table 6. For each policy in the table, there is a coloured square corresponding to the colour-code categorisation assigned by the researchers. These colour codes are also presented in Table 9 for all policies and ECA interventions.

4.2.1. Provision of information and awareness raising

A core aspect of compliance promotion that is found in most of the policies analysed for this report relates to the provision of information to duty-holders and to make reporting on measures and implementation publicly available. This right of access to information is the core of the **Aarhus Convention (H, 1998)** which requires its parties to establish systems for information flow to the public and to ensure the information is sufficient, updated and actively communicated, thereby enabling compliance. However, the role of CCLA in such promotion activities is not specified in the convention. Likewise, the **Public Access to Environmental Information Directive (H, 2003)** require EU Member States to ‘take necessary measures’ to ensure dissemination of and public access to environmental information. The document text suggests that citizens (via CCLA or CGD) can provide information but does not otherwise suggest a pathway for providing or disseminating it.

Many of the thematic policies also specifically require systems for public information, for example the **National Emission reduction Commitments Directive (Z, 2016)** which requires information about national air pollution control programmes and national emission inventories to be made public. However, there is no indication of whether or how citizens can support the transmission of the information to the public using CCLA (e.g. through awareness-raising campaigns or other educative activities), or whether the availability of information may enable CCLA for the purpose of compliance promotion (such as engaging with the emitters or take legal actions). The **Regulation on Deforestation-Free products (D, 2023)** also establishes information requirements for different actors, including the operators and Member States. The **Single-Use Plastics Directive (Z, 2019)** requires Member States to take ‘awareness raising measures’ to ensure consumers and users are informed about re-use systems and appropriate waste management options to prevent littering and other disposal that could lead to marine litter. The means for providing this information are not specified.

Access to information can be understood as a prerequisite for public participation, which must be enabled in the EU for environmental matters in accordance with the **Aarhus Convention (H, 1998)**. Combined with other EU policies not assessed in this study such as Directive 2003/98/EC on the reuse of public sector information (PSI) and Directive 2014/24/EC on public procurement, there exists a foundation for the sharing of data to the public that is not necessarily related to environmental matters (OECD, 2018). However, the specific relation between a requirement to provide information to the public, and the possibility of public participation, for CCLA to contribute to compliance promotion is more tenuous, especially because implementation of such policies is a national competence, and thus will vary across countries (OECD, 2018). It raises

questions about whether the mere requirement of providing information is enough in itself to imply that the policy is supporting the development of CCLA for compliance promotion of other policies. It could be argued that such requirements do not contribute to supporting CCLA if the policy does not allow for the involvement of CCLA in providing the information.

In conducting our policy analysis for this report, we have included requirements to provide information as a potential indicator of CCLA in compliance promotion. This is based on the assumption that access to information may be important, although not necessary, for encouraging the use of CCLA for ECA (for example, such information may enable citizens to develop raising-awareness or education materials about a particular policy). More specifically, we have considered that a broad, unrestricted requirement indicates a possible, but limited opportunity for CCLA (i.e. category ‘yellow’) whereas limitations (e.g. to the types of recipients of information) hint to a potential restriction (i.e. category ‘orange’). An example of the first is the **Habitats Directive (B, 1992)**, which provides for proper consultation of the public concerned, whereas an example of the latter is the **FLEGT Regulation (D, 2005)** that restricts access to information to those responsible for monitoring.

4.2.2. Public participation

Public participation was identified as another core aspect of compliance promotion, but it is less common than information provision and often limited to specific parts of the policy. Here we also note that there are different levels or degrees of participation, from simply being consulted on a matter to actively being involved in decision-making (see e.g. Arnstein, 1969).

In the horizontal policies (i.e. on access to information, public participation, access to justice or on the environmental assessment of plans or projects), aspects of compliance promotion are more prominent than in the vertical policies. The focus on the integration of the public is also more front and centre. A core instrument is undoubtedly the **Aarhus Convention (H, 1998)** as it requires platforms for early public participation to be provided in cases of environmental decision making, planning and developing programmes. It also says that authorities are required to ‘take due account of the outcome of public participation. The **Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (H, 2014)** requires EU Member States to “ensure [that] effective public participation in the taking of decisions enables the public to express” and to foster “participation, including participation by associations, organisations and groups, in particular non-governmental organisations promoting environmental protection” as well as the promotion of environmental education of the public.

There are also examples of specific requirements for public participation in the ‘vertical’ policies. For example, the **Invasive Alien Species Regulation (B, 2014)** requires opportunities for public participation in the development of action plans by EU Member States, while the **Convention on Biological Diversity (B, 1992)** provides for public participation during the environmental impact assessment of proposed projects. The **Habitats Directive (B, 1992)** says that “if appropriate”, national authorities should obtain the opinion of the general public before agreeing to a management plan.

The **Regulation on Deforestation-free products (D, 2023)** also explicitly opens for public participation, although in the specific context of partnerships and collaborations with third countries. The Regulation is the only of the policies analysed so far that not only talks about ‘the public’, but further specifies that “all stakeholders, including civil society, indigenous peoples, local communities, women, the private sector including microenterprises and other SMEs, and smallholders” should be able to participate fully in partnerships and cooperation. Two policies appear to go even further and to provide most opportunities for CCLA to be used in compliance promotion: **The Bathing Water Directive (Z, 2006)** that states that “Member States shall

encourage public participation in the implementation of this Directive”, whereas the **Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (B, 2022)** calls for the adoption of “[p]rovisions for integrating and aligning private and public actions into implementation”.

Table 6. Selected results extracted from policy analysis template on CCLA in compliance promotion.

Policy	Assessment of CCLA in compliance promotion
Horizontal (cross-cutting) policies	
<p>Aarhus convention (H, 1998)[#]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Convention requires contracting parties to establish systems for information flow to the public and to ensure the information is sufficient and updated, allows consumers to make choices (e.g., active dissemination). - Moreover, they should ensure that “environmental information progressively becomes available in electronic databases which are easily accessible”. - Also, NGOs can serve as observers to meetings of the parties. - In the case of environmental decision making, planning, developing programmes, the concerned public shall be informed and platforms for early public participation shall be provided. - The Convention enables compliance promotion by making contracting parties ensure that environmental information is made accessible, timely, and communicated to the public. - In addition, authorities are required to ‘take due account of the outcome of public participation,’ indicating that public participation is an indicator of compliance. - Thus, it appears that there are extensive opportunities for CCLA.
<p>Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive (H, 2001)[*]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The ‘public’ is broadly defined in the directive as “one or more natural or legal persons and, in accordance with national legislation or practice, their associations, organisations or groups”. - There is a requirement that a draft plan or programme and the environmental report prepared in accordance with the directive is made available to the public. - In addition, there is an obligation of consultation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o the public is more narrowly defined as those ‘affected or likely to be affected’ or ‘having an interest’, and ‘including relevant non-governmental organisations’; o that public must “be given an early and effective opportunity within appropriate time frames to express their opinion on the draft plan or programme and the accompanying environmental report” before their adoption. - Moreover, the consultation “shall be taken into account during the preparation of the plan or programme and before its adoption or submission to the legislative procedure.” - Finally, Member states must inform about the adoption of a plan or programme but have discretion in the way they make the information to the public. - Thus, this seems to indicate two-way communication.

Policy	Assessment of CCLA in compliance promotion
Access to Environmental Information Directive (H, 2003) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Member states are required to “take necessary measures” to ensure dissemination and access to public of environmental information. It is unclear whether necessary measures can include CCLA. - Under the article on exceptions, the law states that Member States may refuse to disclose requested environmental information to protect personal data or the person who supplied that information voluntarily or if that person has not consented to the release of the information. This suggests individuals can voluntarily supply environmental information to authorities and consent to its dissemination as part of compliance. - Thus, we concluded that the directive appears to open for one-way communication.
Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (H, 2014)# 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Directive puts forward a list of information that shall be made available to the public concerned, within reasonable timeframes. - The Directive also requires that the effective participation of the public concerned in the decision-making procedures is ensured. To do so, it states that “the public shall be informed electronically and by public notices or by other appropriate means, of the following matters early in the environmental decision-making procedures”. - In addition, the preamble also establishes that “participation, including participation by associations, organisations and groups, in particular non-governmental organisations promoting environmental protection, should accordingly be fostered, including, inter alia, by promoting environmental education of the public”. - Thus, we concluded that this provided several opportunities for CCLA.
Environmental Crime Directive (H, 2024) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Directive requires that the judicial decision that relates to the criminal offence committed and the penalties or measures imposed be published <i>if there is a public interest</i>. That interest should be assessed on a case-by-case basis. - Member States must ensure that the information on the progress of the proceedings is shared with the public concerned. - The Directive also requires Member States to take appropriate measures to prevent environmental crimes, including “information and awareness-raising campaigns targeting relevant stakeholders from the public and private sector, as well as research and education programmes”. - It adds that “[w]here appropriate, Member States shall act in cooperation with such stakeholders.” This indicates a possibility for a two-way communication. - Statistical data about the effectiveness of prevention measures must be published by the Member States and by the European Commission. It is not specified however who should have access to the information.

Policy	Assessment of CCLA in compliance promotion
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Otherwise, mechanisms for coordination and cooperation mentioned in the directive are targeting only national authorities. - Thus, we concluded that the directive appears to open for two-way communication.
Vertical (thematic) policies	
<p>Habitats Directive (B, 1992)[#]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Member States are responsible for the measures in the directive, including designating areas for conservation, design management plans and establishing systems for protection of certain species. They should also “promote education and general information on the need to protect species of wild fauna and flora and to conserve their habitats and natural habitats”. - The Member States’ reports to the European Commission every six years on the implementation of measures and evaluation of their impact should be made accessible to the public. - “Measures taken pursuant to this Directive shall take account of economic, social and cultural requirements and regional and local characteristics”. However, a role for citizens in this is not specified. - It is mentioned that “competent national authorities” should agree to a management plan “only after having ascertained that it will not adversely affect the integrity of the site concerned and, if appropriate, after having obtained the opinion of the general public”. The terms ‘if appropriate’ leaves a margin of discretion that could open or restrict the scope of this provision. - Related to re-introducing species, Member States should ensure that it takes place “only after proper consultation of the public concerned”, which may give citizens a voice in the implementation of measures, but the details of these consultations and opinions are not further specified. - Thus, there appears to be some opportunities for CCLA, but no two-way communication.
<p>Convention on Biological Diversity (B, 1992)[#]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Convention indicates that contracting parties can cooperate with other international organisations for education development, dissemination and awareness. What ‘international organisations’ are and whether they can include e.g. NGOs is not specified, however. - The Convention encourages exchange of information, including of traditional and indigenous knowledge, and sharing all publicly available data. - Contracting parties are responsible for facilitating exchange of information from all public sources. This could include information from CCLA, or CCLA could be a forum for facilitation of exchange of information. - Parties also to encourage cooperation through the exchange of training and experts, which can potentially include exchange on CCLA or as a CCLA. - Non-governmental organisations can participate as observers in COPs, except if 1/3 of parties do not support it.

Policy	Assessment of CCLA in compliance promotion
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contracting parties are to allow for public participation during environmental impact assessment of its proposed projects that are likely to have significant adverse effects on biological diversity. However, it is specified that the participation should be done ‘as far as possible’ and ‘where appropriate’, which may lead to some restrictions. - A subsidiary body on Scientific, Technical and Technological Advice is established by CBD, to provide advice on the implementation of the Convention. The membership of this includes government representatives which suggests it is restricted to citizens. - In sum, there appears to be several opportunities for CCLA, but at the same time there are some elements of language that can be interpreted to restrict it.
Birds Directive (B, 2009)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The directive includes many measures to be taken by Member States to protect bird populations, such as designating protected areas and prohibiting actions with negative effects. No other actors are mentioned in promotion of the directive. - References to informing and sharing of information in the directive is mainly between the Member States and the European Commission. However, reporting by Member States to the European Commission every six years on the implementation of measures and status of protected bird species should also be made accessible to the public. - In Implementing decision 2023/695, which specifies the format of the reporting, it is suggested what can be included under main achievements, e.g. “positive changes in public acceptance of biodiversity protection; improved cooperation between authorities, nature conservationists and other interest groups” (Annex 1.1). This indicates that the inclusion of CCLA might be seen as an achievement, but it is not mandated and only specified in the implementing decision, not the directive itself. - Thus, based on the text in the policy document, we could not conclude on whether this opens for any forms of communication and CCLA in promotion or not.
Invasive Alien Species Regulation (B, 2014)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The public must be given “early and effective opportunities to participate in [the] preparation, modification or review” of action plans developed by Member States. - The regulation allows Member States to establish mechanisms for cooperation <i>at the appropriate level</i>. “Such mechanisms may include exchange of information and data, action plans on pathways and exchange of best practice on management, control and eradication of invasive alien species, early warning systems and programmes related to public awareness or education”. The public level could be one ‘appropriate level’, but there is no certainty. - Thus, there appears to be opportunities for two-way communication.

Policy	Assessment of CCLA in compliance promotion
<p>Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (B, 2022)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Framework includes 23 action-oriented global targets for actions toward 2030, many of which include elements of access to information, public participation or access to justice. - For example, contracting parties shall: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o progressively align “all relevant public and private activities, and fiscal and financial flows with the goals and targets of this framework” (Target 14). o ensure that “the best available data, information and knowledge are accessible to ... the public to guide effective and equitable governance, integrated and participatory management of biodiversity, and to strengthen communication, awareness-raising, education, monitoring, research and knowledge management and, also in this context, traditional knowledge, innovations, practices and technologies of indigenous peoples and local communities should only be accessed with their free, prior and informed consent, in accordance with national legislation” (Target 21). o ensure “the full, equitable, inclusive, effective and gender-responsive representation and participation in decision-making, and access to justice and information related to biodiversity by indigenous peoples and local communities, respecting their cultures and their rights over lands, territories, resources, and traditional knowledge, as well as by women and girls, children and youth, and persons with disabilities and ensure the full protection of environmental human rights defenders” (Target 22). - In terms of financing implementation, the Framework looks to enhance the role of collective action to raise financial resources to support implementation. - The Framework also encourages and accepts voluntary financial resources from private actors, which could enable citizen action in the form of fundraising to ensure compliance. - In sum, the Framework seems to provide for several opportunities for using CCLA in compliance promotion.
<p>FLEGT Regulation (D, 2005)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No direct mention of citizens, local communities or population. No direct mention of the right to observe or participate. - The competent authorities shall keep a record of original FLEGT licences, but access to that information is restricted to those responsible for monitoring, i.e. the people or bodies designated by the European Commission, not the public at large. - No specific provision about access to information by the public. - In sum, there are some elements of restriction, but it does not exclude any types of CCLA in compliance promotion.

Policy	Assessment of CCLA in compliance promotion
<p>Regulation on Deforestation-free Products (D, 2023)[#]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The regulation requires Member States to facilitate the exchange and dissemination of relevant information for risk assessments and on best practices. - The Regulation places some obligation on the, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Establishing an information system that shall include the due diligence systems developed by operators; o Providing access to the wider public of “the complete anonymised datasets of the information system in an open format that can be machine-readable and that ensures interoperability, re-use and accessibility”. - Additionally, it states that partnerships and cooperation with third countries shall “ensure public access to forest management documents and other relevant information”. - The regulation states with regards to partnerships and cooperation with third countries where production takes place that there should be full participation of all stakeholders, including civil society, indigenous peoples, local communities, women, the private sector including microenterprises and other SMEs, and smallholders, as well as inclusive and participatory dialogue and possibly other mechanisms, like structured dialogues. - Given that there are elements of access to information and of public participation (although mostly in the context of cooperation with third countries), we see the potential for a two-way communication between citizens and public authorities.
<p>Nitrates Directive (Z, 1991)[#]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The directive does not contain much information about compliance promotion, such as access to information or public consultations. - The directive promotes the establishment of codes of good agricultural practice that can be voluntarily implemented by farmers. - The directive also directs Member States to develop, as necessary, a programme to train and inform farmers to promote the code of good agricultural practice. It is not clear whether this could be facilitated by CCLA. - Thus, based on the text of the directive, we could not identify clear opportunities for CCLA in compliance promotion in the directive.
<p>OSPAR Convention (Z, 1992)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Convention ensures provisions of information to any legal or natural person. - Moreover, the term ‘Best Environmental Practice’, is defined in the appendix of the Convention to include education and outreach to the public about environmental consequences of choices and disposal of certain products. This could be facilitated through CCLA. - However, promotion compliance is mentioned as being the responsibility of the European Commission established by the Convention to assist contracting party to carry out its obligations.

Policy	Assessment of CCLA in compliance promotion
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Moreover, the European Commission may admit, as observers “any international governmental or non-governmental organisation the activities of which are related to the commission”. They do not have a right to vote, but through observer status, citizens could collect information that may support the use of CCLA in compliance promotion. - Thus, we found that there may be some opportunities for the use of CCLA, but no two-way communication.
Bathing Water Directive (Z, 2006) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One of the objectives of the directive is to provide information to the public about bathing water quality. - Some information must be actively disseminated and promptly made available to the public. - The Directive adds that “new technology that allows the public to be informed in an efficient and comparable way on bathing waters across the Community should be applied”. - In addition, Member States are to encourage public participation and ensure opportunities for the public concerned 1) to find out how to participate, and 2) to formulate suggestions, remarks, or complaints. - Thus, we concluded that there are opportunities for two-way communication between citizens and public authorities.
Directive on the reduction of national emissions of certain atmospheric pollutants (Z, 2016)* 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Member states and the European Commission have an obligation to actively and systematically disseminate information to the public about national and EU emission inventories and programmes. - In addition, Member States shall consult the public “on their draft national air pollution control programmes and updates”. The preamble specifies that consultations should take place “at a time when all options regarding policies and measures remain open”. However, it is not clear how the consultation should influence those drafts and updates. - Finally, the Directive establishes a Clean Air Forum that shall provide input on guidance and facilitate implementation. The forum will bring together all stakeholders including industry, civil society, and the scientific community. The terms ‘facilitate implementation’ seem to indicate a clear opportunity for citizen action to participate in compliance promotion. - Thus, we concluded that the directive contained opportunities for a two-way communication.

Policy	Assessment of CCLA in compliance promotion
Single-Use Plastics Directive (Z, 2019) [#] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “The fight against litter is a shared effort between competent authorities, producers and consumers.” - The directive includes a range of different ways by which Member States can encourage compliance, including labelling plastic products and awareness raising on re-usable alternatives, waste management and impact of inappropriate waste disposal to ‘consumers and users’. - It is also specified that Member States should “take awareness raising measures” as well as “incentivise responsible consumer behaviour”. - While it does not say if other stakeholders (and activities such as CA) could contribute to this, it also does not directly exclude those. - Clean-ups costs are covered by EPR schemes only if they are undertaken by “public authorities or on their behalf”. This could open for CCLA for clean-up activities, but this is to be decided at the national level. - Member states are required to inform consumers and users. - The directive does not use the term ‘citizen’ but ‘consumers and users’, but it appears to make sense in this context, and we cannot conclude that it is excluding CCLA. - Thus, the directive appears to provide for one-way communication, whereby competent authorities inform consumers about the consequences of plastic litter, but there are no requirements for authorities to ensure public participation.
Water Framework Directive (B/Z, 2000) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The WFD emphasizes the importance of public participation, including water users, in the development and updating of river basin management plans. - Authorities must ensure that detailed and accessible information about planned measures is disseminated to the public and that regular updates on the implementation of these measures should be made available to keep the public informed. - The general public is to be actively involved in the decision-making process before final decisions on necessary measures are adopted. - Moreover, it says that the European Commission shall convene when appropriate, in line with the reporting cycle, a conference of interested parties on Community water policy from each of the Member States, to comment on the Commission's implementation reports and to share experiences. Participants should include representatives from the competent authorities, the European Parliament, NGOs, the social and economic partners, consumer bodies, academics and other experts. - In sum, we concluded that there is opportunity for two-way communication.

Policy	Assessment of CCLA in compliance promotion
Marine Strategy Framework Directive (B/Z, 2008)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Directive establishes to the need “to ensure the active involvement of the general public in the establishment, implementation and updating of marine strategies”. - Moreover, it requires Member States to ensure that “all interested parties are given early and effective opportunities to participate in the implementation of this Directive.” - Thus, it appears that there is opportunity for two-way communication.
Nature Restoration Regulation (B, D, Z, 2024)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Member States are responsible for meeting restoration targets and finding suitable areas for restoration ‘based on the best available knowledge and the latest scientific evidence.’ - Member States have to establish national restoration plans. The preparation of these plans must be “open, transparent, inclusive and effective” and the public, including all relevant stakeholders, has to be “given early and effective opportunities to participate” in their preparation. Moreover, the plans should summarise how public participation and the needs of local communities and stakeholders have been considered in preparing and establishing the plans. - For the development and implementation of the national restoration plans, Member States are also encouraged to use ‘existing regional institutional cooperation structure(s)’ in relation to marine ecosystems. These structures are not defined but may be platforms where engagement with non-government actors is already facilitated. - The European Commission, “assisted by experts or the EEA”, has to assess the draft national restoration plans developed by the Member States, who have to revise them accordingly. - The European Commission has to set up a ‘dedicated task force’ to support restoration of pollinator populations and disseminate information to Member States, who are encouraged to make rewetting attractive for private landowners, including through facilitating training and advice. Thus, it seems there is some opening for participation of non-governmental actors. - Member States are also required to make public the data generated by monitoring they have to carry out. - In sum, there appears to be several opportunities for two-way communication.

* For these policies, in addition to main text of the policy, we also assessed associated guidance documents and implementing instructions (where relevant).

Policies that went through a review process by more4nature partners in accordance with ‘the review process’ presented above.

4.3. Citizen generated data in compliance monitoring

Monitoring compliance of a policy often consists of measuring and reporting a range of different parameters. This can comprise a combination of data types that are difficult or impossible for citizens to provide, such as the number of plastic items placed on the market nationally and data that can be citizen generated, such as observations of specific bird species. Several of the policies analysed include (in the main body of text or in separate implementing decision documents) requirements for monitoring by the Member States, including about the format of such reporting. The policies' monitoring and reporting frameworks often require information on data sources, but it does not necessarily restrict the use of CGD.

Some key points from the analysis conducted for each policy are summarised in Table 7 below. For each policy in the table, there is a coloured square corresponding to the colour-code categorisation assigned by the researchers. These colour codes are also presented in Table 9 for all policies and ECA interventions.

The most explicit mention of CGD is found in the most recent policy that we analysed, namely the **Nature Restoration Regulation (B, D, Z, 2024)**. It requires Member States to operate monitoring systems using electronic databases and geographic information systems, which should notably access and use citizen science data. Other policies are less unequivocal. The **Regulation of Deforestation-free Products (D, 2023)** specifies that information submitted by “NGOs and third parties, including indigenous peoples, local communities and civil society organisations” can be considered by the European Commission when assessing risk level of countries. Another potential opening for CGD in the regulation is the formulation that authorities can use “observation data such as from the Copernicus programme and tools or from other publicly or privately available relevant sources” where appropriate. Similarly, the **OSPAR Convention (Z, 1992)** states that “any international governmental or non-governmental organisation the activities of which are related to the commission” can be admitted as observers, meaning that they can collect data on progress of implementation of the convention. It is specified that the monitoring can include scientific progress that is considered useful and generated on initiative of research institutions or through national and international research programmes. This requires certain methods and institutional collaboration but could for example open possibilities for CGD within a research programme.

Other directives are much less explicit regarding the conducting of monitoring and types of data sources. For example, the **Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (H, 2014)** does not mention or encourage use of CGD but mentions that competent authorities should also consider “unsolicited” information from “other sources”. The **Nitrates Directive (Z, 1991)** says that available scientific and technical data should be used in action programmes but does not define sources or quality assurance of the data. It also says that action programmes can be modified “in light of experience gained in implementing the action programmes”, which may open for CGD data sources on such experience.

The **Single-Use Plastics Directive (Z, 2019)** also does not specify the sources for data, however the type of information that is required to be reported may be somewhat restricting. For example, the directive requires data on fishing gear placed on the market, collected single-use plastics (SUP) beverage bottles by weight and consumption reduction of SUP products – information that typically can come from municipalities, recycling schemes or industry statistics. The reporting format asks for information about the “parties involved in the data collection” and data sources may include surveys and “other sources”. The methodology for the monitoring is not defined, but the European Commission will produce a quality check report to assess the data collection and methodology for all Member States.

Table 7. Selected results extracted from policy analysis template on CGD in compliance monitoring.

Policy	Assessment of CGD in compliance monitoring
Horizontal (cross-cutting) policies	
Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive (H, 2001)* 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring is explicitly left to the Member States, but the means are not specified. - However, the directive says that the Member States can make use of “existing monitoring arrangements ... with a view to avoiding duplication of monitoring”. This could potentially include CGD, but it is not possible to conclude on this. - The guidance document opens the door for data to come from a variety of sources, including ‘private organisation’ and ‘environmental NGOs’. At the same time, it acknowledges that the directive “leaves this question open”. - Thus, we could not conclude whether CGD could be used, because the margin of interpretation left to the Member States is too wide. - <i>NB: we discussed that, based on the text of the guidance document, it appears to lean towards ‘yellow’.</i>
Access to Environmental Information Directive (H, 2003) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The directive aims to guarantee access to information to the public, so monitoring compliance concerns the actual access. - The only relevant provision seems to be one requiring Member States to report “on the experience gained” in the application of the directive. However, there is no information about whose experience should be reported on. - Thus, based on the text of the directive, we could not conclude on whether CGD could be used in compliance monitoring.
Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (H, 2014)# 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The main provisions of the directive contain little elements about the possible use of CGD in compliance monitoring. - However, the preamble states that assessments of environmental effects “may be supplemented by the authorities and by the public likely to be concerned by the project in question”. - It adds that “taking into account unsolicited comments that might have been received from other sources, such as members of the public or public authorities, even though no formal consultation is required at the screening stage, constitutes good administrative practice.” - In addition, the preamble also says that the report by the developers has to be prepared by ‘competent experts’ and competent authorities must have ‘sufficient expertise’ to be able to assess the report. This does not exclude as such recourse to CGD. - Thus, we concluded that there could be room for the use of CGD, but it does not seem to be considered as a practice to be formalised.

Policy	Assessment of CGD in compliance monitoring
Environmental Crime Directive (H, 2024) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Member States have to monitor the effectiveness of their prevention measures based on anonymised statistical data on the reporting, investigative and judicial stages. The statistical data should, “as a minimum, include existing data”. Such data include number of criminal offences, of dismissed cases, natural and legal persons who are prosecuted, convicted and fined. Member States have to have a system in place for the recording, production and provision of the data, but it does not say whether anyone outside of national authorities can collect it. - The European Commission shall adopt implementing measures establishing a standard, easily accessible and comparable format for the transmission of statistical data. Whether this can open for collecting or using CGD remains unclear. - Although there is a mention of data collection and use, it is unclear from the text of the Directive whether CGD could be part of such data. It appears that Member States can interpret the Directive to allow or restrict data from sources other than governmental. - Thus, based on the text of the directive, we concluded that we could not determine how these provisions would be interpreted at the national level.
Vertical (thematic) policies	
Habitats Directive (B, 1992)# 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assessments of sites and monitoring of habitats and species populations are key parts of the Habitats directive, as this guides both selection of sites and conservation measures. The effect of measures should also be reported and assessed. - The Member States are required to undertake surveillance of the conservation status of habitats and species, and to establish a monitoring system for the incidental capture and killing of specified animal species. - Every six years the Member States shall report on conservation measures, evaluation of the impact of those measures, and the main results of the surveillance. The report should be made accessible to the public. - The reporting format or types of data are not specified in the directive, meaning that it is not clear whether CGD can be part of the data or not, but there are no indications that it is restricted. - In sum, the margin of discretion of Member States appears too wide to conclude that there is any opening or restriction for CGD in monitoring.
Convention on Biological Diversity (B, 1992) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Convention requires that parties “as far as possible and as appropriate” monitor, through sampling and other techniques, the components of biological diversity. - The Convention says that contracting parties should identify components of biological diversity that are important for conservation, and provides a list of indicators that can be referenced, to monitor. - Contracting parties shall monitor through ‘sampling and other techniques’ the chosen components of biological diversity. This

Policy	Assessment of CGD in compliance monitoring
	<p>suggests monitoring is a national competence and decision, with some flexibility around the methods used.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We could see some elements that could point towards opening or restricting the use of CGD, but it is too unclear and depends largely on the interpretation at the national level. - Therefore, based on the text of the directive, we concluded that it was too difficult to determine how these provisions could be interpreted.
<p>Birds Directive (B, 2009)*#</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The directive emphasises the role of research to achieve the protection of birds and habitats. It does not specify in what way this research should be conducted, by whom or how the information is gathered. - The Implementing decision 2023/695 specifies the format of the reporting on the directive by Member States and what type of information is required, such as a national bird atlas, national bird monitoring overview, national bird red list and other relevant publications. - The methodology and sources of information required is often not specified. The reporting format suggests “published papers, unpublished data held in databases, websites and expert working groups” as examples of data sources, which appear to include CGD. There is also the option to report information “based mainly on expert opinion, with very limited data”. - The implementing decision include references to publications by the NGO BirdLife International and the EBCC Atlas of European Breeding Birds that include volunteer contributions. - Therefore, it appears that the directive opens for the use of information from databases and other sources that could potentially include CGD.
<p>Invasive Alien Species Regulation (B, 2014)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Member states are required to establish a surveillance system of invasive alien species of Union concern or include it in their existing system. - They shall collect and record data on the occurrence in the environment of invasive alien species by survey, monitoring or other procedures. This seems to potentially open for the use of CGD. - Also, the regulation says that Member States may establish mechanisms for cooperation <i>at the appropriate level</i>. “Such mechanisms may include exchange of information and data, action plans on pathways and exchange of best practice on management, control and eradication of invasive alien species, early warning systems and programmes related to public awareness or education”. The public level could exist, but not necessarily. - Thus, we concluded that there might be some (though limited) opportunities for the use of CGD.

Policy	Assessment of CGD in compliance monitoring
<p>Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (B, 2022)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Framework contains a target regarding ensuring that the best information, knowledge, and data are available to both decision makers and the public to, among other things, strengthen monitoring. - In addition, there is a provision to raise awareness among all sectors and actors, while enabling their active engagement in the implementation and monitoring of the Framework and its targets and goals - While these provisions demonstrate some inclusivity within monitoring, they do not contain explicit language about the use of CGD in compliance monitoring. - Although not all guidance documents for this Framework were reviewed in-depth, it must be noted that Decision 15/5 on the monitoring framework for the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework contains clear and explicit language about developing guidance on the use of citizen science, community-based monitoring and information systems, and other sources of data to fill spatial and temporal data gaps. It is possible that other guidance documents not reviewed further elaborate on the topic. - Thus, we concluded that, there is a clear opportunity for the use of CGD in monitoring based on the documents reviewed.
<p>FLEGT Regulation (D, 2005)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a provision for a ‘third-party monitoring’ system through which a person or body monitors and reports on the operation of the FLEGT licensing scheme. - This system appears to be limiting, but it says nothing specifically about using CGD to assess FLEGT. - There are no specific requirements for quality of data, certification requirements, specific expertise. - In sum, there is not enough information to conclude on whether CGD could be used for compliance monitoring. It appears up to the ‘third party’. - <i>However, we discussed that there might be an element of restriction that could also lean towards the categorisation as ‘orange’ instead of grey.</i>
<p>Regulation on Deforestation-free Products (D, 2023)#</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In the assessment risk level of countries by the European Commission, the following information can be taken into account: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o information submitted by the country concerned, regional authorities concerned, operators, NGOs and third parties, including indigenous peoples, local communities and civil society organisations; o whether the country concerned makes relevant data available transparently; and, if applicable, the existence, compliance with, or effective enforcement of laws protecting human rights, the rights of indigenous peoples, local communities and other customary tenure rights holders; - Moreover, the Regulation says that authorities must perform checks of compliance using, where appropriate, “observation data such as

Policy	Assessment of CGD in compliance monitoring
	<p>from the Copernicus programme and tools or from other publicly or privately available relevant sources”.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thus, we concluded that clear opportunities exist for using CGD in compliance monitoring.
<p>Nitrates Directive (Z, 1991)[#]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The only element to be found regarding data in monitoring relates to action programmes. It is stated that available scientific and technical data should be used in action programmes. This seems rather restrictive, but not necessarily excluding CGD at all, e.g. it does not say anything about the quality. - Action programmes can be modified “in light of experience gained in implementing the action programmes” suggesting that CGD could be used to show action programmes are insufficient. - Thus, based on the text of the directive, we could not conclude whether CGD could be used in compliance monitoring.
<p>OSPAR Convention (Z, 1992)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The contracting parties shall be responsible for carrying out monitoring but can take into account “scientific progress which has been made elsewhere on the initiative of individual researchers and research institutions”. This seems to provide opportunities for CGD. - Moreover, the European Commission should develop “collaborative monitoring and assessment related research” and seek “the advice or services of competent regional organisations and...competent bodies to incorporate research”. This could potentially include CGD. - Also, the Convention states that the contracting parties are required to establish joint programmes to transmit scientific or technical research to the Commission, including results of their joint research or ‘other relevant research’. The contracted parties are directed to transmit that information to the commission using a standard procedure. The term ‘other relevant research’ in particular could open for CGD. - Thus, we concluded that there appears to be some opportunities for the use of CGD in compliance monitoring.
<p>Bathing Water Directive (Z, 2006)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The monitoring specified in annex I refers to ISO methods of analysis and quality classifications (Annex II). This could indicate a restriction to the use of CGD because ISO methods are not easy to work with. - Member states must submit a report, which shall have ‘particular regard to’ ... “other scientific, analytical and epidemiological developments relevant to the parameters for bathing water quality, including in relation to viruses”. It is very unclear whether the use of CGD could be opened or restricted. - In sum, the provisions about monitoring do not specify anything directly about the use of CGD, but there are some indications that it could be restricted, notably by requiring the use of ISO methods.

Policy	Assessment of CGD in compliance monitoring
Directive on the reduction of national emissions of certain atmospheric pollutants (Z, 2016)* 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are two main compliance monitoring pathways: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Member states need to submit an informative inventory report where they need to cite their sources of data. There are no explicit restrictions of sources of data for the content of national emission inventories for the pollutants, which indicates an opening for CGD to be used as a source of data. o The monitoring of negative impacts of air pollution shall take a cost-effective and risk-based approach. CGD could be considered a 'cost-effective' approach. - Thus, we concluded that there might be some though limited opportunities for the use of CGD.
Single-Use Plastics Directive (Z, 2019)*# 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Member states are responsible for monitoring and reporting. The format of the reporting and monitoring data is specified in three different implementing decisions. - Monitoring data mainly concerns the number (or weight) of items put on the market, collection rates and reduction of consumption of certain products. However, there is no obligation to monitor the items banned by the directive. - We therefore assume that some information can probably not be provided by citizens (e.g. information about tonnes of plastics placed on the market), while other data could potentially come from CGD (e.g. 'surveys' or 'other' data sources). - The reports should also include data verification and control procedures to ensure reliability of the data. - The reporting formats include a "description of the parties involved in the data collection" and "name of institution" implying that third parties can be involved, but whether this could be citizens is not clear from the text of the directive or the implementing decisions. - In sum, there appears to be some opportunities for the use of CGD, but it is not possible for us to conclude on whether citizens could collect the kind of data required by the directive.
Water Framework Directive (B/Z, 2000) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring programmes of chemical and ecological status of water bodies are key to ensure that the objectives of the water framework directive. It is not directly stated whether CGD can be part of this monitoring. - The directive specifies that "Member States shall monitor parameters which are indicative of the status of each relevant quality element. (...) Estimates of the level of confidence and precision of the results provided by the monitoring programmes shall be given in the plan". - It also states that the methods for monitoring these parameters "shall conform to the international standards listed below in so far as they cover monitoring, or to such other national or international standards which will ensure the provision of data of an equivalent scientific quality and comparability." This may include some element of restriction for using CGD in the monitoring of specific parameters. - However, there are several mentions of using other data or other relevant information. For example, the directive states that Member

Policy	Assessment of CGD in compliance monitoring
	<p>States shall use “any other relevant information including existing environmental monitoring data to carry out an assessment” of the expected environmental quality. The term ‘other information’ may open for the use of CGD.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are more than 30 guidance documents to the WFD developed and revised by a number of working groups. These are not part of this analysis. - Thus, based on the text of the directive, we concluded that there seems to be some opportunities for using CGD in compliance monitoring.
<p>Marine Strategy Framework Directive (B/Z, 2008)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The directive contains provision on monitoring programmes for the ongoing assessment of the environmental status, the elaboration of which is specified in Annex V that notably establishes the “need to develop technical specifications and standardised methods for monitoring at Community level, so as to allow comparability of information”. This appears to limit the use of CGD. - In addition, it specifies that “monitoring programmes shall be compatible within marine regions or subregions and shall build upon, and be compatible with, relevant provisions for assessment and monitoring laid down by Community legislation, including the Habitats and Birds Directives, or under international agreements.” This may restrict the use of CGD because the methodology is complicated. - In sum, based on the text of the directive, we concluded that there are elements of restrictions to using CGD in compliance monitoring.
<p>Nature Restoration Regulation (B, D, Z, 2024)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - With regard to restoration of pollinator populations, Member States must “ensure that monitoring data comes from an adequate number of sites to ensure representativeness across their territories”. The Regulation further requires Member States to “promote citizen science in the collection of monitoring data where suitable and provide adequate resources for the performance of those tasks.” This is a clear push for using CGD in compliance monitoring. - At the same time, Member States have to provide a standardised approach for collecting data on pollinator species, which may – depending on how it is implemented at national level – prevent or discourage the collection of CGD for monitoring or, on the contrary, support CGD being used by authorities because they may appear more reliable. - Member State also have to operate monitoring systems using electronic databases and geographic information systems, and have to “maximise the access and use of data and services from remote sensing technologies, earth observation (Copernicus services), in-situ sensors and devices, or citizen science data, leveraging the opportunities offered by artificial intelligence, advanced data analysis and processing.” - Thus, we concluded that clear opportunities exist for using CGD in compliance monitoring. There are even direct mentions of ‘citizen science’ and ‘citizen science data’.

*For these policies, in addition to main text of the policy, we also assessed associated guidance documents and implementing instructions.

Policies that went through a review process by more4nature partners in accordance with ‘the review process’ presented above.

4.4. Citizen & community-led actions and citizen generated data in compliance enforcement

Compliance enforcement is a key aspect of ECA, but it is also one that typically falls almost entirely to the competence of the Member States, who may adopt administrative, civil or criminal measures to address issues of non-compliance. Although some policies include specific provisions about enforcement, in particular regarding penalties in case of infringements to obligations, most of them refer the matter to the national level.

Generally, we found that enforcement was largely not regulated in Z/B/D policies at EU level. Many policies did not include any provisions about it, and the provisions that we found essentially referred to the national level. At the international level, however, we found that access to justice was more often specified. We expect that this is because the EU and its Member States are all parties to the **Aarhus Convention (H, 1998)** that notably regulates access to justice in environmental matters. Moreover, the rule of law, which requires that “all public powers always act within the constraints set out by law, in accordance with the values of democracy and fundamental rights, and under the control of independent and impartial courts” is enshrined in Article 2 of the TEU. Therefore, there is a general assumption that all EU Member States have administrative, civil and criminal procedures in place to respond to cases of legal non-compliance. Such assumption does exist at international level. This may also explain that the EU deforestation prevention policies, which regulate import from third countries, contain the most elaborate provisions about compliance enforcement.

We summarise the main findings for each policy regarding both CCLA and CGD in compliance enforcement in Table 8 below. For each policy in the table, there are two coloured squares (i.e. the first one for CCLA and the second for CGD) corresponding to the colour-code categorisation assigned by the researchers. These colour codes are also presented in Table 9 for all policies and ECA interventions.

4.4.1. Citizen & community-led actions in compliance enforcement

From the perspective of horizontal policies, in addition to the **Aarhus Convention (H, 1998)** and the **Public Access to Environmental Information Directive (H, 2003)** provides clear opportunities for the use of CCLA in compliance enforcement by providing two avenues for reviewing claims against authorities who deny access to information: one administrative and one legal. This is significant because the directive concerns environmental information held by or for public authorities, thus including information related to Z/B/D policies. The **Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (H, 2014)** also establishes a review procedure “before a court of law or another independent and impartial body established by law”. It specifies that non-governmental organisations shall have access to that procedure. Finally, the most recent EU horizontal policy, the **Environmental Crime Directive (H, 2024)**, requires that appropriate procedural rights are ensured to several actors, including “persons affected or likely to be affected by the criminal offences”, “persons having a sufficient interest or maintaining the impairment of a right”, and “non-governmental organisations that promote environmental protection and meet requirements under national law”.

Few policies explicitly state that the public shall have access to justice, thus allowing citizens to engage in compliance enforcement. One example is the **Regulation on Deforestation-free Products (D, 2023)** allows citizens to bring concerns about non-compliance to the authorities. In addition, it requires authorities to follow up. Furthermore, in some cases, members of the public (identified as witnesses or experts) can be called upon in arbitration to provide evidence, further contributing to compliance enforcement. In some policies with established conferences, committees, forums, citizen groups or organisations can participate as observers, and use such opportunities to inform decision makers. The **Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (B, 2022)** also calls contracting parties to provide access to justice that ensures “full, equitable, inclusive, effective and gender-responsive representation and participation”.

Conversely, the **OSPAR Convention (Z, 1992)**, contains language that indicates enforcement actions are restricted for CCLA. It contends that Contracting Parties, rather than other actors, shall be primarily responsible for determining compliance and bringing disputes to the Convention.

4.4.2. Citizen generated data in compliance enforcement

Provisions related to compliance enforcement are often minimally described in the analysed policies, and generally refer to the national level. It could be that it was not really considered appropriate to regulate at the EU or international level, because enforcement – whether administrative, civil or criminal – is largely seen as a national prerogative. If CCLA in compliance enforcement appears to be addressed in some of the policies we analysed, it was particularly difficult to find provisions that indicated whether CGD could be either encouraged or restricted. However, we found some provisions that could be interpreted in favour of using CGD in this context.

For example, the **Aarhus Convention (H, 1998)** establishes the right for parties in arbitration to provide the tribunal with “all relevant documents, facilities and information” and to receive the evidence of witnesses or experts. The Convention is one of the horizontal (cross-cutting) policies that we analysed. The EU and its Member States are all contracting parties to the Convention, and therefore its provisions apply across the board to all EU environmental policies (including Z/B/D policies), which would hence not need to repeat them.

The **Environmental Crime Directive (H, 2024)** adds another layer to the EU legal framework on procedural rights when it comes to criminal proceedings concerning environmental criminal offences. It requires that Member States have to adopt measures to support and assist any persons reporting criminal offences, and protect them from being persecuted for reporting offences or cooperation in the criminal proceedings. In addition, Member States have to make offenders liable for destroying evidence, or intimidating witnesses or complainants. This appears to be a way of securing the use of evidence (that may include CGD) in environmental criminal proceedings

The only thematic policy that we analysed where this particular right to call for witness or expert to provide evidence in compliance enforcement was found at the international level, in the **Convention on Biological Diversity (B, 1992)**. The Convention requires parties to the dispute to facilitate the work of the arbitral tribunal notably by enabling, when necessary, to call witnesses or experts and receive their evidence. It should be mentioned that this Convention is also signed by parties that are not covered by the Aarhus Convention.

There was one notable exception to the lack of clear opportunities for using CGD in compliance enforcement, however, which was found in the **Regulation on Deforestation-free products (D, 2023)**. Indeed, the regulation provides for a unique procedure whereby citizens can bring ‘substantiated concerns’ about non-compliance to competent authorities, which not only have to

follow-up, but also can decide on interim measures to address the potential non-compliance thus identified.

Table 8. Selected results extracted from policy analysis template on CCLA and CGD in compliance enforcement

Policy	Assessment of CCLA and CGD in compliance enforcement
Horizontal (cross-cutting) policies	
<p>Aarhus convention (H, 1998)*</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Convention establishes that the public has access to administrative or judicial procedures, which “may be ensured by granting members of the public standing to directly enforce environmental law in court”. This may open for CCLA, but it appears to be ultimately up to the Member States to decide. - In addition, the public has access to justice via review procedure before a court of law if their request for information has been ignored. This also appears as an opportunity for CCLA. - It specifies that NGOs are “deemed to have rights capable of being impaired”. - Moreover, in arbitration, parties shall enable “where necessary to call witnesses or expert” to provide with all relevant documents, facilities and information. Thus, it seems that CGD could be used in arbitration provided one of the parties decides to call witnesses or experts. - Thus, we concluded that there are some opportunities for both CCLA and CGD to be used for compliance enforcement.
<p>Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive (H, 2001)*</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Directive establishes that Member States shall “bring into force the laws, regulations and administrative provisions necessary to comply with this Directive”. - Thus, we could not conclude whether CCLA or CGD could be used for compliance enforcement.
<p>Access to Environmental Information Directive (H, 2003)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applicants requesting information and who are refused it can access a procedure to review the request for information. The procedure shall be expeditious and either free of charge or inexpensive, - In addition, applicants shall have access to a review procedure before a court of law or independent body for acts or omissions of the public authority. - The directive defines applicants as ‘any natural or legal person requesting environmental information’. - Thus, we concluded that there is a clear opportunity for CCLA in compliance enforcement, but we could not conclude on the use of CGD.

Policy	Assessment of CCLA and CGD in compliance enforcement
Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (H, 2014) [#] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The directive establishes that members of the public concerned shall have access to a review procedure “before a court of law or another independent and impartial body established by law to challenge the substantive or procedural legality of decisions, acts or omissions subject to the public participation provisions of this Directive.” - It adds that non-governmental organisation shall also have access to review procedure. - Moreover, Member States shall ensure that practical information is made available to the public on access to administrative and judicial review procedures. - Thus, we concluded that there are some opportunities for CCLA in compliance enforcement, but we could not conclude on the use of CGD.
Environmental Crime Directive (H, 2024) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Member States have to ensure that “persons affected or likely to be affected by the criminal offences” and “persons having a sufficient interest or maintaining the impairment of a right”, as well as “non-governmental organisations that promote environmental protection and meet requirements under national law”, have appropriate procedural rights in proceedings concerning those offences. - Member States are also required the necessary measures to support and assist any persons reporting criminal offences, providing evidence or otherwise cooperating with competent authorities. - The preambulatory text adds that there should also be protection from being persecuted for persons reporting environmental criminal offences or for their cooperation in the criminal proceedings. - Moreover, the Directive requires Member States to take the necessary measures to ensure that destroying evidence, or intimidating witnesses or complainants is considered aggravating circumstance for the offender. - The protection of people providing evidence and of witnesses can be seen as a way of recognising the use of CGD in enforcement procedures. - Thus, we concluded that there appears to be some opportunities for CCLA, and to a lesser degree, of CGD in compliance enforcement.
Vertical (thematic) policies	
Habitats Directive (B, 1992) [#] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The directive says that Member States shall establish special areas of conservation involving appropriate statutory, administrative or contractual measures. - A range of actions should be prohibited by the Member States to protect certain species, such as deliberate capture, killing or disturbance of animal species, and cutting, uprooting or destruction of plants species. There are also other measures suggested where deemed necessary, including hunting and fishing rules, license systems and other regulations. - Regarding how to enforce these prohibitions, the directive simply states that Member States “shall bring into force the laws,

Policy	Assessment of CCLA and CGD in compliance enforcement
	<p>regulations and administrative provisions necessary to comply with this Directive”. No penalties or other actions are specified.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thus, based on the text of the directive, we could not conclude whether CCLA or CGD could be used for compliance enforcement.
<p>Convention on Biological Diversity (B, 1992)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Convention provides that disputes are to only take place between contracting parties, which does not indicate anything about a possible role (or restriction thereof) of CCLA in enforcement. - As part of a dispute, there can be evidence given by witnesses or experts, which could indicate some opportunities for using CGD, but only if the citizens are called as witnesses or experts. - The Convention requires contracting parties to inform about potential grave threats to biodiversity but does not open for the possibility of citizens alerting about them at this level. Such a system could potentially exist at the national level. - Thus, we concluded that there are some opportunities for CGD in compliance enforcement, but we could not conclude on the use of CCLA.
<p>Birds Directive (B, 2009)**</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The directive specifies a list of actions that should be prohibited by the Member States, but enforcement mechanisms or penalties are not specified in the directive. - Based on the text of the directive, we could therefore not conclude whether CCLA or CGD could be used in compliance enforcement.
<p>Invasive Alien Species Regulation (B, 2014)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The regulation states that Member States shall establish provisions on penalties for infringements and ensure their application. The regulation requires that penalties are “effective, proportionate and dissuasive”. - This is not enough to conclude on whether citizen science could contribute in compliance enforcement.
<p>Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (B, 2022)*</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One of the Framework targets “to be initiated immediately and completed by 2030” says to ensure “full, equitable, inclusive, effective and gender-responsive representation and participation in decision-making, and access to justice”. - However, this is not specified further and there are otherwise no mentions of means of enforcement in the main text of the Framework. - Thus, although there is very little detail on the role of CCLA in compliance enforcement, there are some opportunities stemming from the target about full representation and access to justice. - However, we could not conclude whether CGD could be used for compliance enforcement.
<p>FLEGT Regulation (D, 2005)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Member states shall establish provisions in penalties for infringements and ensure their application. The Regulation requires that penalties are “effective, proportionate and dissuasive”. - This is not enough to conclude on whether CCLA or CGD could contribute in compliance enforcement.

Policy	Assessment of CCLA and CGD in compliance enforcement
Regulation on Deforestation-free Products (D, 2023) [#] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Regulation directly provides the right for ‘natural or legal persons’ to bring substantiated concerns about non-compliance to the authorities, with a requirement for the authorities to diligently and impartially assess those concerns. - Those concerns as well as ‘other relevant information’ can be the basis for competent authorities to take immediate interim measures to stop identified potential non-compliance. - In addition, the Regulation provides that ‘natural or legal persons’ that have a sufficient interest may have access to court “to review the legality of the decisions, acts or failure to act of the competent authorities”. - However, the Regulation does not specify anything regarding the use of CGD in enforcement, neither opening for it nor restricting it. - Thus, we found clear opportunities for CCLA and CGD to be used for compliance enforcement.
Nitrates Directive (Z, 1991) [#] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The directive only states that Member States must “bring into force the laws, regulations and administrative provisions necessary” to ensure compliance. - Thus, based on the text of the directive, we could not conclude whether CCLA or CGD could be used for compliance enforcement.
OSPAR Convention (Z, 1992) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Convention contains only provisions about contracting parties, and the role of the European Commission. Hints that it could be difficult to have any citizens involvement at all. - Thus, based on the text of the Convention, we could not conclude whether CCLA or CGD could be used for compliance enforcement.
Bathing Water Directive (Z, 2006) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are no provisions about enforcement in the text of the directive, which is to be transposed into national law by the Member States. - Thus, based on the text of the directive, we could not conclude whether CCLA or CGD could be used for compliance enforcement.
Directive on the reduction of national emissions of certain atmospheric pollutants (Z, 2016) [*] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The directive mentions no explicit or implicit inclusion of CGD in enforcement. - The Directive leaves Member States in charge of laying down the rules on penalties. The only requirement is that “penalties provided for shall be effective, proportionate and dissuasive”. - Thus, we could not conclude whether CCLA or CGD could be used for compliance enforcement.

Policy	Assessment of CCLA and CGD in compliance enforcement
Single-Use Plastics Directive (Z, 2019)*# 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enforcement is left to Member States, i.e. rules for penalties and infringement, but no mention of any role for citizens in this. It is only specified that “the penalties provided for should be effective, proportionate and dissuasive”. - As mentioned in the section on monitoring, there is no reporting procedure or monitoring for the banned items in the Directive. - This is not enough to conclude on whether citizen science could contribute for compliance enforcement.
Water Framework Directive (B/Z, 2000) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Member states shall determine penalties applicable to breaches of the national provisions adopted in line with the directive. Further, it requires that penalties are “effective, proportionate and dissuasive” (Art. 23). - The preambulatory text suggests that existing national and regional legislation ensure enforcement for this directive, indicating that the use of CCLA or CGD in enforcement is not clarified directly in this Directive. - Thus, we could not conclude whether CCLA or CGD could be used for compliance enforcement.
Marine Strategy Framework Directive (B/Z, 2008) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Directive establishes that Member States shall “bring into force the laws, regulations and administrative provisions necessary to comply with this Directive”. - Thus, based on the text of the directive, we could not conclude whether CCLA or CGD could be used for compliance enforcement.
Nature Restoration Regulation (B, D, Z, 2024) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific enforcement mechanisms are outlined in the regulation, but access to justice is mentioned in the preambulatory text as a requirement from the Aarhus Convention. - The preambulatory text indicates that not achieving restoration outcomes does not amount to failure to comply as long as suitable measures have been put in place. - Thus, based on the text of the directive, we could not conclude whether CCLA or CGD could be used for compliance enforcement.

* For these policies, in addition to main text of the policy, we also assessed associated guidance documents and implementing instructions (where relevant).

Policies that went through a review process by more4nature partners in accordance with ‘the review process’ presented above.

4.5. Summary of categorisation of policies using colour codes

Table 9 below summarises the findings and assessments of the selected policies related to the different types of intervention of ECA and inclusion of C&CACCLA and/or CGD. This classification is the result of an assessment made collectively by the authors of this report based on our reading of the selected policies. Other partners of the more4nature project were not

involved in discussions about the colour-code categorisation presented below. In the table, the policies are classified first by theme (in alphabetical order, i.e. B, D, Z, B/Z and other) and then by date of adoption.

Table 9. Overview of key findings for citizen & community-led actions (CCLA) and citizen generated data (CGD) in compliance promotion, monitoring and enforcement of selected policies

Policy	CCLA in promotion	CGD in monitoring	CCLA in enforcement	CGD in enforcement
Horizontal (cross-cutting) policies				
Aarhus Convention (H, 1998) [#]				
Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive (H, 2001) [*]				
Access to Environmental Information Directive (H, 2003)				
Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (H, 2014) [#]				
Environmental Crime Directive (H, 2024)				
Vertical (thematic) policies				
Habitats Directive (B, 1992) [#]				
Convention on Biological Diversity (B, 1992)				
Birds directive (B, 2009) ^{*#}				
Invasive Alien Species Regulation (B, 2014)				
Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (B, 2022)				

Policy	CCLA in promotion	CGD in monitoring	CCLA in enforcement	CGD in enforcement
FLEGT Regulation (D, 2005)	Orange	Grey	Grey	Grey
Regulation on Deforestation-free Products (D, 2023) [#]	Green	Green	Green	Green
Nitrates Directive (Z, 1991) [#]	Grey	Grey	Grey	Grey
OSPAR Convention (Z, 1992)	Yellow	Yellow	Orange	Grey
Bathing Water Directive (Z, 2006)	Green	Orange	Grey	Grey
Directive on the reduction of national emissions of certain atmospheric pollutants (Z, 2016) [*]	Green	Yellow	Grey	Grey
Single-Use Plastics Directive (Z, 2019) ^{*#}	Yellow	Yellow	Grey	Grey
Water Framework Directive (B/Z, 2000)	Green	Yellow	Grey	Grey
Marine Strategy Framework Directive (B/Z, 2008)	Green	Orange	Grey	Grey
Nature Restoration Regulation (B, D, Z, 2024)	Green	Green	Grey	Grey

* For these policies, in addition to main text of the policy, we also assessed associated guidance documents and implementing instructions (where relevant).

Policies that went through a review process by more4nature partners in accordance with section '3.1.2The review process' above.

NB: Meaning of the colour code categorisation (see also Table 5 above):

Green: Some form of CCLA or CGD is explicitly	Yellow: No apparent restrictions.	Orange: Some elements of restriction. E.g.	Red: Clearly restricted e.g. because the	Grey: No assessment possible at EU/
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mentioned /encouraged (e.g. public participation). Two-way communication	Basic/indirect enabling of CCLA or CGD in ECA (e.g. provision of information). One-way communication	requirements of expertise or quality that may be interpreted in a way that impedes CCLA or CGD	actors specified do not include the public. Little to no communication	international level
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4.6. Overarching takeaways

In this section, we present some key takeaways based on the analysis of the selected policies (see Table 3). From this review, we summarise our current understanding of the status quo regarding the role of CCLA and CGD in Z/B/D policies and their monitoring frameworks related to ECA.

4.6.1. Using citizen science in ECA is not explicitly restricted

This analysis demonstrates that EU and international Z/B/D policies, and horizontal policies on access to information, public participation, access to justice and environmental assessments do not clearly restrict the use of citizen science initiatives in ECA. Across the policies, there are instances of policy design that opens for one-way or two-way participation between public authorities and citizens or community groups; there are also instances of language suggesting this participation or engagement is restricted. In other cases, we assessed that public participation was neither restricted nor encouraged at the level of the policy documents. This leaves a fragmented landscape of opportunities at the national level of implementation for citizen science initiatives to more effectively engage with or contribute to ECA, which is an overall barrier for citizen science initiatives.

One significant finding, however, is that across all the policies that were analysed in this report, there are no instances where the language suggests a clear or absolute restriction or prohibition of CCLA or CGD to be used in the ECA process. This indicates that despite the challenges citizen science initiatives may currently face in practice, the door appears open, at least in theory.

4.6.2. How to achieve ECA is vaguely defined and largely left to the national level

Most of the policies that were analysed in this report include provisions regarding ECA, but they are often vague and referring to the Member States or contracting parties to take the steps to determine and ensure such a process at national level. There is generally a wide margin of discretion left for interpreting and operationalising those provisions. For example, an EU policy would typically require Member States to ‘ensure’ that information is made available to the public or ‘encourage’ the active involvement or participation of all interested parties. How information is made available, and who makes it available is often left open. Yet it is those aspects that may determine whether CCLA can play a role in compliance promotion.

Likewise, policies might include some specifications about what is to be monitored or reported, about procedures to be followed or use terms like ‘other relevant information’ or ‘other sources’, but they would not clearly specify that data may or may not come from citizens. We found that some policies appear to provide opportunities for using CGD in compliance monitoring, such as the Nature Restoration regulation, whereas others seem to rather restrict such use. Thus, implementation at the national level may vary and greatly influence whether opportunities or

restrictions identified for CGD in compliance monitoring in the text of EU or international laws materialise. At EU level, the freedom of interpretation of Member States may be quite important (in particular with directives) but it is not absolute. They are bound by the objectives of law and incorrect application may lead the European Commission to taking legal action, in the form of an infringement procedure, on the basis of the institution's own investigations or following complaints from citizens, businesses or other stakeholders (Article 258 TFEU; see also Eliantonio, 2023).

Most of the policies we analysed contained very few provisions about compliance enforcement. Some even simply referred to the national level to “bring into force the laws, regulations and administrative provisions necessary to comply” with the policy. Some contained some guiding principles, like the need to put in place “effective, proportionate and dissuasive” penalties. Few of them contained provisions requiring access to justice. Those were essentially to be found in the horizontal policies, in international policies and in policies about deforestation prevention. We assume that the inclusion of such provisions in the last two categories is motivated by the fact that contracting parties or third countries would not necessarily have in place the system of rule of law that is one of the cornerstones of the EU.

Generally, we found that information about ECA is difficult to identify and extract from the text of policies, because policies are not explicit about what relates to ECA. Also, the language used in the policies is often vague and open to interpretation. As a result, Member States are left with a wide margin of discretion in the interpretation and implementation EU or international policies, which may lead some countries deciding to promote the use of citizen science in ECA, while others choose to restrict it.

Moreover, we often found more (and more precise) information in implementing decisions or guidelines than in the main text of the policies. However, a full overview of such decisions and guidelines, which can be numerous, is demanding even for policy experts. It appears likely that researchers, practitioners and members of the civil society may struggle to find them or even remain unaware that they exist. This means that in practice, the usefulness of such documents in terms of supporting ECA may be unduly limited.

4.6.3. Main policy obstacles to using CCLA and CGD in ECA

Across the assessed policy documents, we identified various potential obstacles that may restrict the use of citizen science in ECA. An obstacle that is common to several policies pertains to which actors, outside of the public authorities, could participate in or have competence for certain processes important for compliance. The language of the policies is often too vague to conclude decidedly on whether citizens could be included or not as actors of compliance. With the exception of the monitoring framework for the **Montreal-Kumming Global Biodiveristy Framework (B, 2022)** and of the **Environmental Crime Directive (H, 2024)**, the policies we analysed did not use the terms ‘citizen science’, ‘citizen actions’ or ‘citizen generated data’, but many used the term ‘public’ or equivalent.

More specifically, we found that, while most policies include some provisions about access to information (one-way communication), some form of (unrestricted) public participation (two-way communication) is rarely mentioned or encouraged. However, CCLA may promote the policies and encourage central actors to comply in any way they can even if this is not specified in the policy. The fact that the policy exists and that there are provisions and requirements that public authorities (and other actors) can be held accountable to, may in itself enable CCLA.

Another type of obstacle that also finds its base in the vagueness of the policy language is related to the collection of data that can be used for monitoring or to inform policy changes. Several policies used terms such as ‘experts’, ‘technical or scientific requirements’ or ‘best practices’ that

may be interpreted differently by different actors. Some might see a requirement of ‘scientific data’ as a restriction to the use of CGD, while others might consider that citizen science methods to generate data can be scientifically sound and methodologically defensible. Without defining these terms (the definition of which is likely to evolve over time), such language can be interpreted by the authorities (or by the national legislators transposing EU law) as limiting the use of CGD in compliance monitoring or enforcement, because of uncertainty regarding their quality or scientific value. Likewise, a reference to an otherwise undefined ‘third-party monitoring system’ (as in the **FLEGT Regulation (D, 2005)**) leaves much uncertainty about the potential use of CGD in such system. As the recognition of the role and legitimacy of citizen science evolves, some of the vague terms that appear to indicate restriction may in the future be interpreted differently and more inclusive of citizen science initiatives.

4.6.4. Potential opportunities for CGD or CCLA in ECA

There are some examples in the policies analysed for this report where citizen science initiatives appear more clearly encouraged for ECA. By their very nature, the horizontal (cross-cutting) policies, like the **Aarhus Convention (H, 1998)** and the **Access to Environmental Information Directive (H, 2014)** contain general provisions about the role of citizens in ECA that apply to all environmental policies. They notably provide clear opportunities for the use of CCLA in compliance promotion and enforcement, in the form of provisions about access to information, public participation and access to justice. In addition, there was language indicating the potential use of CGD in compliance enforcement, with provisions about the use of evidence from witnesses and experts in non-compliance procedures (e.g. arbitration). The **Environmental Crime Directive (H, 2024)** also contains provisions that open for two-way communication in compliance promotion as well as for the use of CCLA (and to a lesser extent to CGD) in compliance enforcement.

Thematic policies often refer to the horizontal policies with regards to access to information, public participation and access to justice, but they can also contain more specific provisions. For example, with regards to the use of CGD in compliance monitoring, the **Nature Restoration Regulation (Z/B/D, 2024)** is the only of the policies we have analysed that is explicit about their use. In the regulation, the access and use of data, including CGD, should be maximised by Member States in operating monitoring systems on the basis of electronic databases and geographic information systems. Moreover, Member States are encouraged to use and provide resources for citizen science in monitoring, and in other assessed policies using terms, such as ‘other information’ or ‘other relevant research’ that can be used in monitoring.

Generally, most opportunities were identified for the use of CCLA in compliance promotion, with policy measures about public access to information, consulting the public or giving an observer role to non-governmental organisations (one-way communication) during planning and policymaking processes, or even requiring the development of mechanisms for public participation (two-way communication).

At EU level, one policy clearly stood out as providing most opportunities for the use of citizen science and in all the types of ECA interventions: the **Regulation on Deforestation-Free Products (D, 2023)**. Our understanding is that this may be both due to the fact that it is the one of the newest policies that we have analysed (thus may reflect current priorities) and that the policy concerns deforestation prevention, which involves third countries where access to information, public participation and access to justice may not be ensured by other policies as the EU with the Aarhus Convention. In any case, this regulation appears to provide a good example of how policies in other areas could better take into account citizen science in ECA.

At international level, the **Convention on Biological Biodiversity (B, 1992)** and **Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (B, 2022)** both provide interesting opportunities for using citizen science in ECA, though neither provide clear opportunities for CCLA or CGD in all types of ECA interventions. It should be noted that a decision (15/5) on the monitoring framework for the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework contains clear and explicit language about developing guidance on the use of citizen science, community-based monitoring and information systems, and other sources of data to fill spatial and temporal data gaps. This is one of the only direct mentions of citizen science we found, even if it is not directly in the main text of the Framework.

All in all, due to the current lack of clarity in the policies, it remains nevertheless difficult to conclusively determine whether and how the use of CCLA and CGD in ECA will be implemented in practice at the national level..

4.6.5. Key factors influencing the policy content

It appears that the role of citizens tends to be more present in more recently adopted thematic instruments compared to older ones. Moreover, compliance appears more clearly defined in Regulations than in Directives at the EU level. The **Regulation on Deforestation-Free Products (D, 2023)** is one of the policies that most clearly includes opportunities for both CCLA and CGD in ECA. It is also one of the newest policies included in this report as it was adopted in 2023 (and will enter into force in November 2024), and a regulation. Furthermore, the **Nature Restoration Regulation (B, D, Z, 2024)** adopted in June 2024 explicitly mentions ‘citizen science’ and ‘citizen science data’, notably in the context of provisions about monitoring and reporting.

Likewise, at the international level, the **Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (B, 2022)** includes strong and clear language on two-way engagement and public participation in compliance promotion and compliance monitoring. Although the **Convention on Biological Diversity (B, 1992)**, which is among the oldest policies we analysed, contains interesting provisions with regards to CCLA in compliance promotion and CGD in compliance enforcement, the wording is clearly different than what one might find in more recent instruments.

In comparison, older policies such as the **Nitrates Directive (Z, 1991)** and the **Habitats Directive (B, 1992)** include little to no provisions about access to information or reporting. However, it is not yet possible with the limited selection of policies analysed to conclude that there is a clear trend towards more recognition of the role of citizen science initiatives in ECA in more recent policies.

There is also a large variation in the language and key terms between the policies belonging to different sectors and topics (Z/B/D/H). This makes comparison and analysis across policies challenging. The terms and language used also differ between different aspects of compliance promotion, monitoring or enforcement.

Detailed requirements for promotion, reporting and monitoring are often not included in the policy itself, but for some policies, such as the **Single-Used Plastics Directive (Z, 2019)** and the **Birds Directive (B, 1992)**, this is described in detail in accompanying guidelines, implementing decisions and similar documents, not all of which have been assessed in this report, though they may provide more language on the opportunities for CCLA and CGD in ECA.

5. Conclusions and next steps

Although environmental legislation is often adopted at EU or international level, the responsibility for fully and correctly implementing those rules falls on the national authorities in the respective countries. At the EU level, the concept of ECA aims at supporting Member States to ensure compliance with EU policies. There could be opportunities for citizen science to assist Member States in ensuring compliance, either through CCLA aiming at preventing or correcting non-compliance, or through the use of CGD for monitoring compliance and correcting cases of non-compliance. This report provides a sound understanding – based on a representative sample of international and regional policies – of the status quo in this matter. In the policy analysis conducted for this report, we found that existing international and EU policies tend not to specifically establish a role for citizens to support ECA. We identified various opportunities that could materialize, but this largely depends on the interpretation of the relevant EU and international policies at the national level.

Generally, the mere existence of an environmental policy might be seen as an opportunity in itself for citizen science - in particular CCLA - to be used in ECA. In other words, the opportunity of engaging in CCLA would be enabled by the mere fact that there is a policy in place that establishes compliance obligations that may impact the rights of citizens and communities. Moreover, many types of CCLA, such as the possibility for citizens to engage with media or address national or local authorities, are unlikely to be restricted by an environmental policy in the EU or on the international level.

The horizontal (cross-cutting) policies that we analyse in this report provide a framework for the public to access information, participate in decision-making processes and to have access to justice, in particular in the EU. Although there are very few explicit mentions specific forms of citizen science initiatives, they formalise the right for citizens to be involved in ECA and for authorities to establish communication and participation pathways. These policies are particularly important because they apply to the environmental policy field in its entirety, so that even if a particular thematic (vertical) policy should say nothing about e.g. access to justice, citizens would nevertheless have rights following the Aarhus Convention. On the other hand, thematic policies may also establish more specific provisions than what horizontal policies provide for. Indeed, we found that most of the thematic policies do not (re-)establish the basic rights, but rather tend to specify the type of information that is to be made public or the context of public participation. Some appear to offer increased opportunities for citizens to play a role in ECA, others open the door for possible restrictions, and yet others scarcely mention engagement with or participation from the public, suggesting that such a decision will be left up to Member States.

Generally, we found that the current lack of clarity in the all the policies analysed in this report (horizontal and vertical) makes it difficult for us – and we expect also for national authorities and for citizens and communities – to conclusively determine whether and how the use of CCLA and CGD in ECA is to be implemented and potentially encouraged in practice at the national level. Despite the challenges citizen science initiatives may currently face in practice, we find that the door appears open to more use of CCLA and CGD in ECA, at least in theory.

One of the main outcomes of Task 1.1 and of this report is a tailored methodology (including a template and scoring framework) to identify and assess how language in a policy enables, encourages, or restricts citizen science initiatives in ECA. There remain opportunities to refine the methods further, based on lessons learned in the development of this initial report. Looking forward, we believe there is value in refining the colour-coding framework according to specific topics and indicators emerging across the analysis, which can allow for holistic and contextual

analysis of all the measures within a policy. We also aim to extend as far as possible our policy analysis to the guidance documents for the selected policies. Moreover, Table 9 that provides the overview of key findings for CCLA and CGD in compliance promotion, monitoring and enforcement of the policies could be further refined, adding additional columns about e.g. the actors of ECA for each policy, the duty holders, and expected dates for revision of a particular policy.

In Phase 2 of Task 1.1 (i.e. months 7 to 24) of the more4nature project, we will develop the methodology further and conducting analysis of more international and EU policies. In addition, we will be developing a template for assessments of national policies and their implementation, and we will support project partners in charge of the more4nature case studies to conduct the policy analysis in their respective jurisdictions. We aim to establish and maintain a dialogue with WP3 (Case studies) and Task 4.5 (Strategic engagement of policy makers and national agencies) to identify opportunities in existing policies or for changing policies whenever relevant. This work aims to develop a comprehensive analysis and a replicable methodology that can be applied to other policy areas, deepening our collective understanding of the diverse opportunities and barriers to CCLA and CGD in ECA across Europe and beyond.

6. Annexes

6.1. Legally binding and non-legally binding international and EU legal instruments of relevance for the more4nature project

Level	Policy/law	Zero pollution	Biodiversity protection	Deforestation prevention	Horizontal
Legally binding EU instruments					
EU	Aarhus Regulation				x
EU	Access to Environmental Information Directive				x
EU	Public Participation Directive				x
EU	Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive				x
EU	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive				x
EU	Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive				x
EU	Environmental Impact Assessment Directive				x
EU	Directive on Protection of the Environment through Criminal Law				x
EU	INSPIRE Directive				x
EU	Birds Directive		x		
EU	Habitats Directive		x		
EU	Invasive Alien Species Regulation		x		
EU	The Zoos Directive		x		

Level	Policy/law	Zero pollution	Biodiversity protection	Deforestation prevention	Horizontal
EU	Plant Protection Products Regulation		x		
EU	Biocidal Products Regulation		x		
EU	Regulation on deforestation-free products			x	
EU	FLEGT Regulation			x	
EU	LULUCF Regulation			x	
EU	Renewable Energy Directive			x	
EU	Forest Reproductive Material Directive			x	
EU	Single-Use plastics Directive	x			
EU	Single-Use plastics Implementing Regulation	x			
EU	<i>Proposal for a Regulation preventing plastic pellet losses to reduce microplastic pollution</i>	x			
EU	Directive on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe	x			
EU	Directive on the reduction of national emissions of certain atmospheric pollutants	x			
EU	Water Framework Directive	x			
EU	Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)	x			

Level	Policy/law	Zero pollution	Biodiversity protection	Deforestation prevention	Horizontal
EU	Bathing Water Directive	x			
EU	Nitrates Directive	x			
EU	Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive	x			
EU	<i>Proposal for a Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation</i>	x			
EU	Directive on plastics bags	x			
EU	Delegated Regulation on plastic waste shipments	x			
EU	Directive on arsenic, cadmium, mercury, nickel and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in ambient air	x			
EU	Floods Directive	x			
EU	Drinking Water Directive	x			
EU	Industrial Emissions Directive	x			
EU	European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR)	x			
EU	Directive on the Sustainable Use of Pesticides	x	x		
EU	<i>Proposal for a Regulation on the Sustainable Use of Pesticides (withdrawn February 2024)</i>	x	x		
EU	REACH Regulation	x	x		
EU	Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive	x	x		

Level	Policy/law	Zero pollution	Biodiversity protection	Deforestation prevention	Horizontal
EU	Waste Framework Directive	x	x		
EU	Port Reception Facilities Directive	x	x		
EU	Ship-source pollution Directive	x	x		
EU	Nature Restoration Regulation	x	x	x	
Legally binding international instruments					
UNEC E	Aarhus Convention				x
UN	Convention on Biological Diversity		x		
IUCN	Convention on Wildlife Trade (CITES)		x		
UNEP	Convention on Migratory Species		x		
UNESCO	RAMSAR Convention on Wetlands of International Importance		x		
UN	United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD)		x		
UNFCCC	Warsaw Convention for REDD+			x	
Regional	OSPAR Convention	x			
UNEC E	Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution (CLRTAP)	x			
UN	Basel Convention	x			
UN	<i>Proposed Plastic Treaty</i>	x			

Level	Policy/law	Zero pollution	Biodiversity protection	Deforestation prevention	Horizontal
UNFC CC	Paris Agreement	x		x	
UNFC CC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)	x		x	
Non-legally binding EU instruments					
EU	EC Action Plan for Environmental Reporting				x
EU	Biodiversity strategy for 2030: Bringing nature back into our lives		x		
EU	Biodiversity Strategy 2030: Barrier Removal for River Restoration		x		
EU	2023 Communication on the revised EU Pollinators Initiative: A new deal for pollinators		x		
EU	EU Green Infrastructure Strategy		x		
EU	2018 EU Pollinators Initiative		x		
EU	Common Fisheries Policy		x		
EU	Blue economy and maritime spatial planning		x		
EU	Action plan: Protecting and restoring marine ecosystems for sustainable and resilient fisheries		x		
EU	EU forest strategy for 2030			x	
EU	Farm to Fork Strategy			x	

Level	Policy/law	Zero pollution	Biodiversity protection	Deforestation prevention	Horizontal
EU	2013 EU Forest strategy			x	
EU	EU Plastics Strategy	x			
EU	Chemicals strategy	x			
EU	Textiles strategy	x			
EU	Zero pollution action plan	x			
EU	Commission Communication - A Europe that protects: Clean air for all	x			
EU	EU biodiversity strategy for 2030		x	x	
EU	Bioeconomy Strategy		x	x	
EU	Climate Change Adaptation Strategy	x		x	
EU	Second Circular Economy Action Plan	x	x		
EU	Environment action programme to 2030	x	x	x	
EU	Communication on The European Green Deal	x	x	x	
Non-legally binding international instruments					
UNEP	Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework		x		
UN REDD	Reduced Emission from Deforestation and Forest Degradation (REDD+)			x	
UNECE	Amsterdam Declaration			x	

Level	Policy/law	Zero pollution	Biodiversity protection	Deforestation prevention	Horizontal
UNFC CC	New York Forest Declaration			x	
UN	UN Strategic Plan for Forests			x	
UNEA	Resolution 'End Plastics Pollution' 5/14	x			
UN	Agenda 2030	x	x	x	x
UN	SDG14 - Life below water	x	x		
UN	SDG 15 - Life on land	x	x	x	
UNEC E	San Marino Declaration	x	x		
UNFC CC	Clean Development Mechanism (CDM)	x		x	

6.2. Template for analysis of EU and international policies in more4nature

***more4nature**

T1.1 – Policy context

Mapping and analysing EU and international Z/B/D-related policies in terms of their fitness to facilitate the integration of citizen generated data (CGD) and citizen & community-led actions (CCLA) in environmental compliance assurance

TEMPLATE FOR DATA COLLECTION FOR POLICY ANALYSIS

NB: Please open in desktop version to be able to use drop-down menus.

We welcome any questions or feedback to this template!

Recommendation: start with analysis of the articles, then check the Preamble afterwards to see if relevant

Step 1: Contact Details

Please provide the following details about the individual conducting the assessment:

First reviewer of this policy (NIVA)	
Name:	
Institute:	
E-mail:	
Date:	
Note:	

Second reviewer of this policy (partner)	
Name:	
Institute:	
E-mail:	
Date:	
Note:	

Step 2: Policy details

Fill in the details about the policy you are analysing.

Main policy document	
Policy name	
Link to the policy document	
Main policy objective (Z, B and/or D policy?)	Choose an item. ...
Aim(s) of the policy	
Specific targets , e.g. "enhance and restore all bodies of surface water" (WFD)	
Policy instrument , e.g. Aarhus Convention = International Convention; Aarhus Regulation = EU Regulation)	Choose an item.
Date of adoption: Adoption = date at which legislators adopted it, usually appears with the name of the law	
Date of entry into force: Entry into force = specified at the end of EU laws (specific provision)	
Date of revision(s): Revisions/amendments = important to know when the law was revised because important changes can have occurred	
Adopted by	Choose an item. ...
Accompanying guidelines/guidance document/s	
Is the policy accompanied by guidance documents that gives more details about how to conduct compliance?	
What to look for:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guidance (document, reporting, national plans) - Guidelines - Implementation strategies - Monitoring implementing schemes 	

Yes / No NB: If yes, please conduct the rest of the analysis based both on the policy and on the document/s	Choose an item.
Reference (provision in the policy and link to document/s):	
Date of adoption of the document/s	
How often are they being reviewed?	

Step 3: Environmental compliance assurance in/of the policies

Fill in the information about how the policy provides for compliance: please follow the instructions in the tables below.

Compliance promotion

Definition: “range of actions that authorities undertake to help businesses and individuals meet their obligations, and to prevent or reduce infringements and the harm that they cause.”

Keywords to be used for the analysis (not exhaustive list, please use some discretion!):

- Access
- action
- assist*
- availab*
- awar*
- campaign
- communicat*
- compl*
- cooperat*
- disseminat*
- emission
- guid*
- incentiv*
- Inform*
- infrastructure
- integr*
- measur*
- notif*
- particip*
- prevent*
- promot*
- tool*

What does the policy say about compliance promotion?

Keywords match	
Reference (fill in article number (incl. paragraph) where relevant keyword appears and extract of text):	
Please argument your answer considering e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Type of requirements: e.g. shall/may/are encouraged - what preventive measures are to be put in place? - how do public authorities encourage compliance with policy requirements? 	
Which authority/ies does the policy put in charge of promotion?	
Identification of the authorities in charge of promotion (mostly relevant for the national level – but useful to check what EU level says if anything)	
<u>Keywords to be used for the analysis (not exhaustive list, please use some discretion!):</u>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Authorit* - Bod* - Bodies - Contact point(s) - Institution* - Member States - Third party 	
Reference (fill in article no and extract of text):	
Name of authority/ies:	
Level (national, EU and/or international)	
Competences (i.e. what does the policy say that each identified authority can do in term of compliance)	

Compliance monitoring

Definition: “all forms of inspection, surveillance and investigation that may be undertaken to verify compliance or discover and characterise infringements.”

Keywords to be used for the analysis (not exhaustive list, please use some discretion!):

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - access - action - Assess* - Audit* - Collect* - compl* - Inspect* - Investigat* - Monitor* - Observ* - Report* - Study - Surve* - Track* - Verif* 	
What does the policy say about compliance monitoring?	
Keywords match	
Reference (fill in article no and extract of text):	
Please argument your answer considering e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The type of requirements: e.g. shall/may/are encouraged - Monitoring Mechanisms - Reporting Requirements - Audits and Inspections - Certification and Approval Processes 	
Which authority/ies does the policy put in charge of monitoring?	
Identification of the authorities in charge of monitoring (mostly relevant for the national level – but useful to check what EU level says if anything)	
<u>Keywords to be used for the analysis (not exhaustive list, please use some discretion!):</u>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Authorit* - Bod* - Bodies - Contact point(s) - Institution* - Member States - Third party 	
Reference (fill in article no and extract of text):	
Name of authority/ies:	

Level (national, EU and/or international)	
Competences (i.e. what does the policy say that each identified authority can do in term of compliance)	

Compliance enforcement

Definition: “actions by a competent authority to respond to infringements detected, including administrative, civil and criminal law enforcement.”	
<u>Keywords to be used for the analysis (not exhaustive list, please use some discretion!):</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - action - administrative - charges - civil - compl* - Correct* - criminal - Enforc* - Fail* - fee/s - Infring* - injunction - Interim (measures) - Judg* - law - legal - penalt* - prohibit* - prosecut* - Sanction* - Shortcoming - violate* 	
What does the policy say about compliance enforcement? <i>Provide any relevant reference (e.g. article number), a short summary of content (using the words found in the law) and short explanation of why this is related to compliance enforcement?</i>	
Keywords match	
Reference (fill in article no and extract of text):	
Please argument your answer considering e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Type of requirements: e.g. shall/may/are encouraged 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enforcement Mechanisms - Dispute Resolution mechanisms - Penalties and Sanctions - Remediation and Corrective Actions 	
Which authority/ies does the policy put in charge of enforcement? Identification of the authorities in charge of enforcement (mostly relevant for the national level – but useful to check what EU level says if anything)	
<u>Keywords to be used for the analysis (not exhaustive list, please use some discretion!):</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Authorit* - Bod* - Bodies - Contact point(s) - Institution* - Member States - Third party 	
Reference (fill in article no and extract of text):	
Name of authority/ies:	
Level (national, EU and/or international)	
Competences (i.e. what does the policy say that each identified authority can do in term of compliance)	

Step 4: Citizen & community-led actions (CCLA) and citizen generated data (CGD)'s contribution to policy compliance

Fill in the information about how the policy you are analysing are opening for or hindering the use of CGD and/or CCLA in environmental compliance assurance. Please follow the instructions in the tables below.

Integration of citizen & community-led actions (CCLA) in compliance promotion

Opportunities or barriers for citizens to support public authorities in the promotion activities, e.g. through information and other awareness raising campaigns, petitions, lobbying, etc.
<u>Keywords to be used for the analysis (not exhaustive list, please use some discretion!):</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - access* - advocacy - anticipation - aware* - campaign*

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - citizen - co-creation - communit* - contribut* - cooperat* - disseminat* - Influence - inform* - initiative - lobby* - On behalf of - particip* - petition - public - qualified - science - self* - social enterprises - transparen* - warning 	
What does the policy say about CCLA in compliance promotion?	
Keywords match	
Reference (insert provision and extract of text):	
Please argument your answer considering e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct reference to citizens, local communities or population - Requirement to provide information - Restrictions to information provisions - Right to observe 	
Does the policy seem to indicate that CCLA in compliance promotion is restricted?	
Reference (insert provision and extract of text):	
Please argument your answer	

Integration of citizen generated data (CGD) in compliance monitoring

<p>Opportunities or barriers for CGD to be used for monitoring activities, such as inspections and surveillance</p> <p>CDG is defined as ‘data generated by people, for people’, meaning that the individuals who stand to benefit from data collection are directly involved in the design, collection, analysis, and use of data that describes them (Citizen-Generated Data: Data by people, for people International Institute for Sustainable Development (iisd.org))</p>	
<p>Keywords to be used for the analysis (not exhaustive list, please use some discretion!):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access* - Bottom-up - citizen - Co- (co-production; co-creation) - collaborative - collection - Community - Consult* - Crowdsourcing - Data - Disseminat* - engag* - experience - indigenous - initiative* - know* - local - Manage* - participat* - public - quality - scien* (scientific; science) - sensor - stakeholders - standards - technical - transparen* - User 	
<p>What does the policy say about CGD in compliance monitoring?</p>	
<p>Keywords match</p>	
<p>Reference (insert provision and extract of text):</p>	
<p>Please argument your answer considering e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Types of monitoring mechanisms (e.g. self-assessment, 	

external audits, reporting...) - reporting requirements (content incl. specific data or metrics, frequency, recipients, etc.) - certification requirements or approval process - requirement of certain quality of data (e.g. scientific...) - requirement of specific expertise - clarity of requirements (margin for interpretation)	
Does the policy seem to indicate that CGD in compliance monitoring is restricted?	
Reference (insert provision and extract of text):	
- Please argument your answer	

Integration of citizen & community-led actions (CCLA) in compliance enforcement

Opportunities or barriers for citizens to support public authorities with enforcement, e.g. through information and other awareness raising campaigns, petitions, lobbying, etc.
<u>Keywords to be used for the analysis (not exhaustive list, please use some discretion!):</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - advocacy - anticipat* - aware* - campaigns - citizen - co* (co-creation, co-production) - communit* - disseminat* - Influence - inform* - initiative* - lobby* - On behalf of - petition - public

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - science - self* - social - transparen* - warning 	
What does the policy say about CCLA in compliance enforcement?	
Keywords match	
Reference (insert provision and extract of text):	
Please argument your answer considering e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - access to justice - right to complain/complaint mechanism - provisions on arbitration - reference to the Aarhus Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-Making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters 	
Does the policy seem to indicate that CCLA in compliance enforcement is restricted?	
Reference (insert provision and extract of text):	
Please argument your answer	

Integration of citizen generated data (CGD) in compliance enforcement

Opportunities or barriers for CGD to be used to support authorities in case of infringements

CDG is defined as 'data generated by people, for people', meaning that the individuals who stand to benefit from data collection are directly involved in the design, collection, analysis, and use of data that describes them ([Citizen-Generated Data: Data by people, for people | International Institute for Sustainable Development \(iisd.org\)](#))

Keywords to be used for the analysis (not exhaustive list, please use some discretion!):

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access - citizen - co (co-created, co-production) - collaborative - collection - collegial (projects) - Communicat* - Community - Complain* - Contractual - Contribut* - Court - Data - enforce* - initiatives - Interest* - Judg* - Justice - lawsuit - Legitimate - method* - public - Scien* - scien* - source - standard* - technical - transparen* 	
What does the policy say about CGD in compliance enforcement?	
Keywords match	
Reference (insert provision and extract of text):	
Please argument your answer considering e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provisions about witnesses in (enforcement) procedures - Evidence to be provided in such procedures - Requirements of quality or reliability of data - Legal standing 	

Does the policy seem to indicate that CGD in compliance enforcement is restricted?	
Reference (insert provision and name of policies (and provisions) that are referred to):	
Please argument your answer	

Step 5: Cross-cutting coherence

Reference to other policies

Some policies may simply refer to an existing policy instead of setting out own rules about e.g. compliance or (more likely) public participation and (possibly) the use of citizen science (for example: "...according to the rules set out in Article ... of Directive ...")

Does the policy refer to other policies with regards to compliance and/or integration of CGD and/or citizens actions, if so, which?

Look at the provisions you have identified (i.e. regarding compliance) in the policies for references to other policies, e.g. explicit reference to Aarhus Convention... (look for the term Aarhus)

Reference (insert provision and name of policies (and provisions) that are referred to):	
Explanation (why is the reference relevant?):	

6.3. Simplified template for policy analysis used at F2F consortium meeting on 28 May 2024

***more4nature**

T1.1 – Policy context

Mapping and analysing EU and international Z/B/D-related policies in terms of their fitness to facilitate the integration of citizen generated data (CGD) and citizen & community-led actions (CCLA) in environmental compliance assurance

TEMPLATE FOR DATA COLLECTION FOR POLICY ANALYSIS

NB: Please open in desktop version to be able to use drop-down menus.

We welcome any questions or feedback to this template!

Step 1: Contact Details

Please provide the following details about the individual conducting the assessment:

Reviewers of this policy	
Name(s):	Rapporteur: Members:
Institute(s):	
E-mail:	
Date:	
Note:	

Step 2: Policy details

Please look for provisions in the text **highlighted in green**, and do not spend more than 15 minutes on this part!

Main policy document	
Policy name	Prefilled
Link to the policy document	Prefilled
Main policy objective (Z, B)	Other, please specify

and/or D policy?)	
Aim(s) of the policy	
Specific targets , e.g. "enhance and restore all bodies of surface water" (WFD)	
Specific indicators The more detailed ways the targets will be assessed	

Step 3: Citizen & community-led actions (CCLA) and citizen generated data (CGD)'s contribution to policy compliance

Please look for provisions in the text **highlighted in yellow**, and make sure you have time to go through all 4 policy attributes.

Integration of citizen & community-led actions (CCLA) in compliance promotion

<p>"Compliance promotion includes the range of actions that authorities undertake to help businesses and individuals meet their obligations, and to prevent or reduce infringements and the harm that they cause. Actions include providing information and advice on how to comply and trying to 'crimeproof' legislation, i.e. designing obligations in a manner that deters infringements from occurring."</p>	
<p>What does the policy say about CCLA in compliance promotion?</p>	
<p>Please argument your answer (either yes or no) considering e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct reference to citizens, local communities or population - Requirement to provide information - Restrictions to information provisions - Right to observe 	

How does the policy relate to CA in compliance promotion?					
Please select (bold) the most appropriate way to summarise your findings (i.e. green, yellow, orange, red or grey)	Some form of CA or CGD is explicitly encouraged	Unclear but no apparent restrictions	Unclear but some element of restriction	Clearly restricted	No assessment possible at EU level

Integration of CGD in compliance monitoring

“**Compliance monitoring** includes all forms of inspection, surveillance and investigation that may be undertaken to verify compliance or discover and characterise infringements.”

What does the policy say about CGD in compliance monitoring?

<p>Please argument your answer considering e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Types of monitoring mechanisms (e.g. self-assessment, external audits, reporting...) - reporting requirements (content incl. specific data or metrics, frequency, recipients, etc.) - certification requirements or approval process - requirement of certain quality of data (e.g. scientific...) - requirement of specific expertise - clarity of requirements (margin for interpretation) 					
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How does the policy relate to CGD in compliance monitoring?

Please select (bold) the most appropriate way to summarise your findings (i.e. green, yellow, orange, red or grey)	Some form of CA or CGD is explicitly encouraged	Unclear but no apparent restrictions	Unclear but some element of restriction	Clearly restricted	No assessment possible at EU level
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Integration of citizen & community-led actions (CCLA) in compliance enforcement

<p>Compliance enforcement: “Follow-up and enforcement involves actions by a competent authority to respond to infringements detected. Effective responses are necessary in order to punish, deter, and remediate damage. Responses may include administrative, civil and criminal law enforcement.”</p>					
<p>What does the policy say about CCLA in compliance enforcement?</p>					
<p>Please argument your answer considering e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - access to justice - right to complain/complaint mechanism - provisions on arbitration - reference to the Aarhus Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-Making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters 					
<p>How does the policy relate to CCLA in compliance enforcement?</p>					
<p>Please select (bold) the most appropriate way to summarise your findings (i.e. green, yellow, orange, red or grey)</p>	<p>Some form of CCLA or CGD is explicitly encouraged</p>	<p>Unclear but no apparent restrictions</p>	<p>Unclear but some element of restriction</p>	<p>Clearly restricted</p>	<p>No assessment possible at EU level</p>

Integration of CGD in compliance enforcement

<p>Compliance enforcement: “Follow-up and enforcement involves actions by a competent authority to respond to infringements detected. Effective responses are necessary in order to punish, deter, and remediate damage. Responses may include administrative, civil and criminal law enforcement.”</p>					
<p>What does the policy say about CGD in compliance enforcement?</p>					
<p>Please argument your answer considering e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provisions about witnesses in (enforcement) procedures - Evidence to be provided in such procedures 					

How does the policy relate to CGD in compliance enforcement?					
Please select (bold) the most appropriate way to summarise your findings (i.e. green, yellow, orange, red or grey)	Some form of CCLA or CGD is explicitly encouraged	Unclear but no apparent restrictions	Unclear but some element of restriction	Clearly restricted	No assessment possible at EU level

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